

**A SOCIOLINGUISTIC SURVEY OF CHAMLING:
A TIBETO-BURMAN LANGUAGE**

A REPORT

SUBMITTED

TO
LINGUISTIC SURVEY OF NEPAL (LinSuN)
CENTRAL DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS
TRIBHUVAN UNIVERSITY, KATHMANDU,
NEPAL

By

Dr. Tara Mani Rai

2017 October

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Map 1: The geographical distribution of the Chamlingin Nepal

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background

The purpose of this research work is to examine the sociolinguistic situation of Chamling, a Rai Kirati language of the Himalayish sub-group within Tibeto-Burman group of Sino-Tibetan language family. Chamling is mainly spoken in the central Khotang and northern most of Udayapur district. However, they seem to have spread across the districts like Taplejung, Panchthar, Ilam, Sankhuwasabha, Bhojpur, Panchthar, Morang, Sunsari, Jhapa and the Kathmandu valley. Although the majority of the Chamling are in the Khotang, where children no longer speak and only the elderly sometimes use this language.

The Chamling language is one of the developing languages in Nepal. This is one of the second largest languages after Bantawa under the Rai group. The term 'Chamling' refers to the people as well as the language they speak. They call their language as *camliŋ la* 'Chamling language'.

It is recognized as the distinct national language (2002 NFDIN Act, No. 20, Section 2C). This language is considered to be closer to the neighboring languages; i.e., Chamling and Puma. There exist three language varieties in the Chamling speaking area, namely Halesi, Ratanchha and Balamta (Ethnologue 2012: 39). The latest Census gives the number of mother tongue speakers as 76, 800 (CBS 2012).

Chamling is classified on the Expanded Graded Intergenerational Disruption Scale (EGIDS) as (6b) *Threatened*. This level of language vitality status is defined as, 'the language is used for face-to-face communication within all generations, but it is losing users' (Lewis, et al. 2015).

This chapter discusses the Chamling people and their mother tongue in particular. It consists of four sections. Section 1.1 deals with the ethnicity, religion, occupation and literacy of Chamling. In section 1.2, we discuss the language, demography, linguistic affiliation and review of earlier works of the Chamling language. Section 1.3 discusses the purpose and goals of the survey. Finally, in section 1.4, we present the organization of the report.

Map 1.1: Chamling speaking area

Source: Ethnologue (2012)

1.1 Ethnicity, geography, religion, occupation and literacy

In this section, we discuss the ethnicity, geography, religion, occupation and literacy in the Chamling speech community.

1.1.1 Ethnicity

The Chamling are one of the aboriginal peoples of Nepal. The equivalent term they use is 'Rodung'. This is one of the subgroup of the Rai whereas the term 'Kirati' covers strictly four distinct indigenous nationalities i.e. Rai, Limbu, Koits-Sunuwar and Yakkha. Since the Rai is an umbrella term, it comprises around 25 languages namely, Bantawa, Chamling, Thulung, Kulung, Khaling, Koyee, Dumi, Sampang, Puma, Wambule, Jerung, Bahing, Nacchiring, Puma, Tilug, Mebahang, Dungmali, Athpahariya, Chhiling, Yamphu, Loharung, Chhintang, Phangduwali, Belhare, Sam.

Diagram 1.1: The status of the Chamling

The Chamling are people of mongoloid stock practicing agriculture and animal husbandry. The major crops are potatoes, maize, and especially millet. The millet made *dhindo* is eaten with cooked vegetables or *kinema* made of soybeans. Meat is occasionally eaten, especially on ritual occasions. Pork is preferred to other meat, a preference that is shared by many Tibeto-Burman families. The Chamlings are fond of drinking alcohol, *wasim- aarakha*.

The Chamling community has exogamous kinship groups referred to as *pats^{ha}* 'little clan'. These kinship groups are based on the aggregates of closely related males and unrelated females, who have been brought into the group from other kinship groups, usually of the same community.

In our field study, we selected five survey points namely Durchhim, Mahadevsthan, Ratanchha, Balamta and Aaptar VDCs of Khotang, Udayapur districts. The survey points are tabulated in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Survey points of Chamling

	Locality	Ward No.	VDC/Municipality	District	Zone
1	Hadunge	4	Durchhim VDC	KHOTANG, UDAYAPUR	SAGARMATHA
2	Halesi	4	Mahadevstha VDC		
3	Kolle	7	Ratanchha VDC		
4	Majhgaun	4	Balamta VDC		
5	Rasuwa	2	Aaptar VDC		

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2014)

1.1.2 Religion

Mostly the Chamling people follow the animism or they prefer to be called the followers of the Mundum based Kirat region. However they are influenced by the Hindu religion. Also there are threats from Christian and other practices like Phalgunanda, Josmani and Heavenly path.

1.1.3 Occupation

The traditional occupation of the Chamling community is agriculture and animal husbandry. Some of them are in the recruitment either in India, British, and Singapore or in Brunei. Others are in teaching professions. In course of time, they are found to have changed themselves in different occupations i.e. government job (civil service), technical service. Few of them are in the local trade. Nowadays, the youngsters are lured to move in abroad.

1.1.4 Literacy rate in sampling

Both literate and illiterate participants were involved during the sociolinguistic survey of Chamling in each survey point. The literacy situation in aggregate (from the five survey points) is presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Literacy in the Chamling speech community

Literacy category of the participants			
Total Participants: (N=60)			
Literate		Illiterate	
45		15	
Female		Male	
30 (50%)		30 (50%)	
Literate	Illiterate	Literate	Illiterate
20	9	25	6
(69%)	(31%)	(81%)	(19%)

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 1.1 presents the fact that out of the total sixty participants from Chamling community, forty-five are literate and fifteen illiterate; thirty female and thirty male. Of the female participants, twenty (i.e. 69%) were literate; and nine (i.e. 31%) were illiterate. Similarly, of the male participants, twenty-five (i.e. 81%) were literate; and six (i.e. 19%) were illiterate.

1.2 Language, demography, linguistic affiliation

1.2.1 Language

The Chamling language is one of the languages of Tibeto-Burman group of Sino-Tibetan language family. Further it has been categorized under the sub group Kirati Rai languages. Till now, many linguists have attempted to classify the Kirat Rai languages of Nepal. However, consistency is lacking in the number of languages. Disagreement among the linguists about the number of the Kirati languages is still ongoing. Unless a detail survey is made, it is impossible to figure out the exact number of the Kirati languages.

In the view of linguistic Typology, Chamling is a polysynthetic (or pronominalized) language, carrying number and person affixes in the verb, sometimes for the agent participant and sometimes for the patient but usually not for both.

1.2.2 Demography

The Chamling speech community is found to have been living mainly in Khotang and Udayapur districts. They are spread over the districts like Taplejung, Sankhuwasabha, Dhankuta, Terhathum, Panchthar, Ilam, Jhapa, Sunsari, Morang, Bhojpur, Okhaldhunga, Solukhumbu, and Kathmandu. This is because of globalization, Chamlings are scattered across the European countries in course of recruitment in Gurkha regiment and other opportunities.

Table 1.4 presents the mother tongues by district according to the census report 2012.

Table 1.4: Chamling mother tongues by district

	District	Population	Percentage
01	Taplejung	154	0.02 %
02	Panchthar	1254	0.00 %
03	Ilam	3011	0.08%
04	Jhapa	1565	1.82%
05	Morang	5036	0.01%
06	Sunsari	5654	0.52%
07	Dhankuta	432	3.91%
08	Terhathum	16	1.63%
09	Sankhuwasabha	1393	0.00 %
10	Bhojpur	2241	0.04%
11	Solukhumbu	52	1.49%
12	Okhaldhunga	12	6.49%
13	Khotang	34105	0.35%
14	Udayapur	20136	0.27%
15	Saptari	12	0.00 %
16	Siraha	63	2.35%
17	Dhanusa	36	0.11%
18	Sarlahi	26	2.23%
19	Lalitpur	426	0.06%
20	Bhaktapur	197	12.48%
21	Kathmanud	811	0.00 %
22	Bara	16	0.01%
23	Parsa	25	0.01%
24	Kaski	13	0.00 %
25	Kailali	45	0.08%
	Total	76,800	100%

Source: Population Census (2012)

1.2.1 Linguistic affiliation

Figure 1.1 shows the linguistic affiliation of the Chamling, a Rai Kirati language spoken mainly in Khotang and Uadyapur districts.

Figure 1.1 : Genetic affiliation of Chamling

Source: Ethnologue (2012)

1.3 Review of earlier works

Winter (1991:111) classifies Chamling under the southern sub-group of Central Kirati languages. Chamling is one of the second largest Kirati languages among the Rai group after Bantawa. Chamling is closely related to the Kirati languages like Puma, Tilung. T.B Rai (1994) gives some information about the Chamling and the people in which he describes the glorious past and neglected present of the language, but provides no linguistic description of the Chamling language.

Ebert's *Camling* (1997) is supposed to be the first major work to describe Chamling in detail. There is linguistic description of Chamling as phonology, the verb, nominals and sentence patterns. Chamling in linguistic map in course of locating some other Rai Kirati languages. She has not added any more information about Chamling people and language.

Pokharel (1999) includes Chamling along with other Kirati languages and dialects like Rakong, Lunam, Puma, Bantawa, Sunuwar, Umbule *Wambule* [italics added], Bahing, Amchoke, Chamling, Thulung, Limbu, Chamling, Kulung, Thami under the theoretical frame 'historical reconstruction'.

Yadava and Turin (2005) shows the genetic affiliation to the Chamling language. This study classifies the Chamling language into the East-Himalayish sub-group of Himalayish group within Tibeto-Burman sub-family of Sino-Tibetan language family.

Kirat Rai Language and Literature Council (2005) is a study based on Swadesh 100 word list. It is a preliminary attempt to the collection of the basic word list of the language. But this study lacks the phonetic transcription based on the IPA chart. Some words are erroneously transcribed, however; it is field based study.

Chamling Rai (ed. 2070 VS) is a collection of Chamling words in which around 1500 words are enlisted. There are provided the instructions for using the wordlists.

Rai (ed. 2055 VS) is a chronicle of Chamling Rai. This is a land mark for the Chamling people because it tells how they were evolved and spread genetically. This is significant from anthropological perspective. This is significant from anthropological perspective.

Chamling (2065VS) is a magazine of Kirat Rai Chamlig Khambatim. This is in bilingual namely Nepali and Chamling. It has covered various genres of literature and thus the activities of the organization. This is a voice of Kirat Rai Chamling Khambatim.

Rai (2068BS) is a Chamling Byakaran (Chamling Grammar) in which is the basic grammatical information of Chamling language. It seems to be very useful for the Chamling language beginners.

Rai (2012) is a descriptive study of Chamling language where he has discussed the phonology, Morphology, syntax including the sociolinguistic situation. He focuses on the speech community of Balamta, Udayapur district.

Rai (2012) is a language loyalty of non-Chamling people which is a PhD dissertation. His focus is on how Chamling people are shifting towards Nepali, a language of wider communication. Not only this, he describes the attitudes of the Chamling Speaking community.

In addition to the above mentioned works, there are some Audio cassettes like *Nana pakune I&II*, *Imo Chhaimari* and some documentaries in Chamling. There are textbooks upto Grade 5 and *Mundhums* available in Chamling initiated by the Chamling people. Chamling language has recently got the access in the mainstream daily newspaper Gorakhapatra and some media like Rupakot FM and Indigenous TV programs.

1.4 Significance of the study

This study is of great significance not only for the Chamling language community, but also for the researchers and the linguists interested in the study of this language. The significance of the study may be enumerated as follows:

- a) The envisaged perspective of this study was to survey the linguistic situation of Chamling. So, this study may help for further research in Chamling language.
- b) This study can help know the current linguistic situation and issues of Chamling.
- c) This study may be useful and beneficial for the academic researcher and general researchers who want to carry out and are interested in Chamling language.
- d) There is a need of detailed language documentation project on Chamling language for preserving and promoting the mother tongue.
- e) There is a need of developing pedagogical grammar and reading materials in Chamling.
- f) This study will be beneficial for the government and governmental organizations to have baseline information about the current linguistic situation of Chamling.

1.4 Purpose and goals

The main purpose of this study is to present the sociolinguistic situation of the Chamling language which has been categorized as an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Nepal. The specific goals /objectives of the study are as follows:

- a) To examine the dialectal variation by assessing the levels of lexical similarity and the levels of intelligibility among the selected varieties in the language;
- b) To look at the vitality of the language by investigating the patterns of language use in certain domains;
- c) To assess the mother tongue proficiency and extent of community bilingualism of Chamling speakers in standard Nepali;
- d) To evaluate the language maintenance and the attitudes of the speakers towards their language; and
- e) To gather information regarding the resources and language development for the implementation of mother-tongue based multilingual education in Chamling.

1.6 Organization of the report

The survey report is organized into seven chapters. Chapter 1 presents general background information about the language including the purpose and goals of the study. In chapter 2, we deal with the methodology used in the survey. Chapter 3 examines the possible dialectal variations in Chamling. In chapter 4, we look at the major domains of language use. Chapter 5 evaluates language vitality, language maintenance and language attitudes. In chapter 6, we look language resources and language development. In chapter 7, we present the summary of the findings and recommendations. The annex includes phonetic symbols, word lists and sociolinguistic questionnaire.

CHAPTER 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.0 Outline

This chapter presents research methodology employed in the survey. It consists of four sections. Section 2.1 presents the overview of the research methodology. Section 2.2 deals with different types of research tools, their basic characteristics and the ways they were employed in the survey. Section 2.3 deals with the survey points, sampling procedure and sample size. And section 2.4 consists of limitations of the survey with respect to time, access, area, methods and participants.

2.1 Overview

This survey employed five different methods/tools in order to fulfill its goals. The methods/tools consist of Sociolinguistic Questionnaire (SLQ), Wordlist Comparisons (WLC), and Participatory Method (PM).

The Sociolinguistic Questionnaire (SLQ) consists of three sets: Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A, Sociolinguistic Questionnaire B and Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C. Participatory Method (PM) comprises four tools: Domains of Language Use (DLU), Multilingualism (ML), Dialect Mapping (DLM) and Appreciative Inquiry (AI).

Table 2.1 presents the major goals of the survey, the research methods/tools used, and a brief description of the methods/tools including the major focus of the tools in the survey.

Table 2.1: Overview of the major survey goals, research methods/tools including the major focus of the tools

	Goals of the survey	Research methods/tools	Brief description	Focus of the methods/tools
1.	To examine the patterns of language use in certain domains; language attitudes, and language vitality; language maintenance, mother-tongue proficiency and multilingualism; and language resources in Chamling	Sociolinguistic Questionnaires (SLQ)	Consisting of three sets: A, B and C	
		Sociolinguistic Questionnaires - A (SLQ A)	80 questions to be administered on individual of different age groups, sex and literacy in at least five points including the core point	Language resources; Mother-tongue proficiency and multilingualism; Domain of language use; Language vitality; Language maintenance; and Language attitudes
		Sociolinguistic Questionnaires -B (SLQ B)	The four tools: DLU , ML, DLM and AI be used in a group of at least eight to twelve participants of mixed category	Domain of language use; Dialect mapping; Multilingualism; Appreciative enquiry
		Sociolinguistic Questionnaires - C (SLQ C)	21 questions to be administered on language activist or village head	Language attitudes; Language maintenance; Language vitality; Language development
2.	To assess the levels of lexical similarity among the selected varieties in the language	Wordlist Comparisons (WLC)	Lexical comparison of 210 words	Lexical variation among selected varieties in the language

2.2 Research methods/tools

2.2.1 Sociolinguistic Questionnaire (SLQ): description, purpose and procedure

Three sets of sociolinguistic questionnaire (i.e., SLQ: A, B & C) in the survey were employed. Their description, purpose and procedure are described in the following paragraphs.

A. Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A (SLQ A)

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A which consists of eighty (80) questions was intended to be administered to the individuals of the speech community. The main purpose of this set was to gather information from the individuals about the language resources, mother-tongue proficiency and multilingualism, domain of language use, language vitality, language maintenance and their language attitudes. The opinions from the individuals are often influenced by factors such as location, education, age and sex.

Prior to the administration of this set, first, the Chamling speaking areas were selected on the basis of geographical location from the core point i.e. Halesi, Durchhim, Ratanchha of Khotang district. Other two points namely Balamta and Aptar are selected from Udayapur district. Likewise the participants were chosen from different categories of age, sex and educational background from each survey points. Figure 2.1 presents a model for sampling of participants from each point in the Chamling speech community.

Figure 2.1: Model for sampling of participants from each point

A₁=15-29, A₂=30-59, A₃= 60+, L= Literate, IL= Illiterate

In Figure 2.1, the term 'point' refers to sociolinguistic field survey points in the speech community. During the sociolinguistic field survey in the Chamling speech community, five survey points were visited. Similarly, (15-29), A₂ (30-59), A₃ (60+) refer to age category; likewise, 'L' and 'IL' to 'literate' and 'illiterate' category of the participants who participated during the discussion and interview in the survey so far. The survey has a specific checklist for the Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A.

1 Table 2.2: Checklist for Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A

Checklist for Sociolinguistic Questionnaire (SLQ-A)											
Point X											
Male						Female					
A ₁		A ₂		A ₃		A ₁		A ₂		A ₃	
L	IL	L	IL	L	IL	L	IL	L	IL	L	IL
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Following the sampling model to the maximum, sixty (60) participants from the Chamling speech community were interviewed with their different age categories, sex and educational background in each linguistic survey point. The questionnaire was administered in Nepali language and the answers given by the participants were recorded in the questionnaire in Nepali and English. After the data collection, the answers were entered into a computer database and analyzed for general patterns and trends that would contribute to fulfilling the research goals.

B. Sociolinguistic Questionnaire B (SLQ B)

Another set of questionnaire was Participatory Method (PM). PM was a tool employed during the survey to elicit information from the Chamling participants. The tools included in the PM were Domains of Language Use (DLU), Multilingualism (ML), Dialect Mapping (DLM) and Appreciative Inquiry (AI). The main purpose of the use of PM tools was to help the Chamling speech community think about the dialects of the Chamling language, how multilingual Chamling people were, in which contexts they employed the Chamling language, and what their dreams and aspirations were for their language development. In the questionnaire, each tool was equipped with well-written systematic procedures for the facilitators in the group. The different components of the **SLQ B** are presented in the following paragraphs.

(I) Participatory Method (PM)

The criteria consisted of the implementation for the participatory tools are as follows:

- a) The group must consist of eight to twelve participants of mixed category of the speech community. Furthermore, it is desirable that there be several women and men in each group having of all ages (15 years and older) in the group with several older, middle aged and younger participants.
- b) The participant must belong to the target mother tongue and his/her; at least, one parent must be from the target language.
- c) The participants must be grown up in the survey point and must have lived in the society currently. If s/he has lived elsewhere, it should not be more than five years and s/he must have lived in the village for the past five years.
- d) Each tool involves the members of the speech community in group-discussion on the sociolinguistic situation of their language.

(II) Domains of Language Use (DLU)

Domains of Language Use (DLU) tool was employed in the Chamling community members during the linguistic field survey. The use of the tool was mainly aimed to help the Chamling community members think and visualize the language that the Chamling people speak in diverse contexts. In this tool, the Chamling participants took part in discussion and thought about the situations in which they employed Nepali, language of wider communication (LWC) and wrote them on pieces of paper. Then, they wrote down the situations in which they speak Chamling language and those situations in which they use both Nepali and Chamling. Then, the participants were asked to place the labels as Nepali, Chamling and both Nepali and Chamling. Next, they were asked to organize the labels in each category according to the situations, which occurred daily and those occurred less than often. At the end, the participants concluded by discussing if they would like to employ each language in any other situations.

(III) Dialect Mapping (DLM)

The main purpose of the Dialect Mapping (DLM) tool was to help the community members think about and visualize different varieties of the Chamling language. During the linguistic field survey, Chamling participants were gathered for group discussion. Then, during the discussion, they were asked to write down the names of

each village on a separate sheet of paper where Chamling is spoken and placed them on the floor to represent the geographical location. Then, they were asked to use the loops of string to show which villages speak the same as others. Next, they were asked to use the number to show the ranking from easiest to understand to most difficult. Then, they were advised to use colored piece of plastic to mark those varieties they understand very well, average and poorly.

(IV) Multilingualism (ML)

Multilingualism tool was employed to help the community members think about and visualize the levels of fluency in both the Chamling language and Nepali by different subsets of the Chamling community. In this community, Nepali language is the most dominant language, which is used for communicating with outsiders. The participants were asked to use two overlapping circles, one representing the Chamling people who speak the Chamling language well. The overlapped circle represents those who speak both languages well. The participants were advised to write down the names of subgroups of people that speak Nepali well.

For each group, they also discussed whether they also spoke the Chamling language 'well' or not 'so well'. Then, they were asked to place them in the appropriate location in circles. After having done this, they were advised to write down the names of the subgroups of Chamling people that spoke the Chamling language 'well', which was increasing and how they felt about that.

(V) Appreciative Inquiry (AI)

Appreciative Inquiry tool was administered to gather information about the dreams and aspirations of the speech community for their mother tongue development. Using this tool, the participants were asked to describe things that make them feel happy or proud about their language or culture. Then, based on those good things in the Chamling language and culture, they were asked to express their dream of making language or culture even better. They were advised to categorize the dreams from the easiest to the most difficult; specify which ones were most important; and to choose a few to start on developing plans such as who else should be involved; what the first step should be; and what resources they needed.

C. Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C (SLQ C)

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C is a set of 21 questions, which was administered to language activists and village heads. The main purpose of this set of questions was to assess the language maintenance, language vitality and their attitudes towards their languages and their readiness for language development. This set was administered to at least two participants in each survey point in Chamling.

2.2.2 Wordlist comparisons: Description, purpose and procedure

The basic wordlist contains 210 items. The main purpose of this wordlist is to determine the thresholds of lexical similarity uniting groups of languages and dialects at various percentage levels on the basis of standard wordlists elicited from the mother tongue Chamling speakers. The results have been presented in Table 3.2 to Table 3.5, which illustrates the relative linguistic distances among various speech communities, and lexical differences have been compared in an exhaustive matrix of pairs.

From each survey points, at least six participants of different age, sex and educational status were chosen. In the selection, those speakers were selected who were born in the village or in the near vicinity, had to speak the Chamling language as his/her mother tongue and should not have lived outside the village for extended periods of time.

For each item on the wordlist, the researchers elicited, in Nepali, the local Chamling word from a Chamling mother tongue speaker. The responses were transcribed using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). Afterwards, the words were entered into the computer software known as Wordsurv (word survey), and the words entered in the WordSurv were exported as WordSurv 6 XML file to Cog for the comparison of the words collected in the five survey points in terms of lexical and phonetic similarity, and the lexical items were compared in order to determine similarities and differences among the varieties sampled.

This tool provides an initial indication of possible dialect groupings in Chamling. However, the intelligibility between dialects cannot be conclusively stated on the basis of lexical similarity percentages.

2.3 Sampling: Survey points, sampling procedure and sample size

2.3.1 Geographical location of the survey points

In the sociolinguistic field survey of the Chamling language, information was taken from the five survey points from different villages of Khotang and Udayapur districts pertinent to the Eastern Development Region of the country.

Table 2.3 presents the geographical location of the survey points recorded by the Global Positioning System (GPS) device.

Table 2.3: GPS for five survey points in Chamling speaking area

	Survey points	Elev.	North	East	Remarks
1.	Durchhim	1,162 m	27 ⁰ 10' 37.5"	86 ⁰ 10' 35.9"	Hadunge
2.	Mahadevsthan	1,375 m	27 ⁰ 11' 27.8"	86 ⁰ 27' 16.6"	Halesi
3.	Ratanchha	1600 m	27 ⁰ 10' 50"	86 ⁰ 50' 23.4"	Kolle
4.	Balamta	1,276 m	27 ⁰ 06' 00.1"	86 ⁰ 40' 14.0"	Majhgaun
5.	Aaptar	2,16 m	27 ⁰ 00' 18.0"	86 ⁰ 45' 06.9"	Rasuwa

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

2.3.2 Sampling procedure

First, the Chamling speaking areas were selected on the basis of geographical location from the core point i.e. Durchhim, Haleshi, Ratanchha of Khotang district and Balamta and Aanptar of Udayapur district. Secondly, the individuals were chosen from different categories of sex, age and educational background from each survey points.

Of the sample points, sixty participants were sampled and interviewed. The age of the participants of Chamling was from 15 to 60 above with their sex and educational background in each linguistic survey point. The questionnaire was administered in the Nepali language and the answers given by the participants were recorded in the questionnaire in Nepali and English.

2.3.3 Sample size

During the field survey, the sociolinguistic information was collected by using the different tools such as Sociolinguistic Questionnaires A, B, C and Wordlist.

Table 2.4 shows the survey points, tools and the number of sheets of information collected from each survey point in the field-study.

Table 2.4: Survey points, tools (at least to be used) in each survey point

Survey Points	Sociolinguistic Questionnaires			Other Tools
	A (Individual)	B (Participatory)	C (Language activists)	Wordlist
Durchhim, Chumakhu	12	✓	2	6
Mahadevstha, Halesi	12	✓	2	6
Ratanchha, Kolle	12	✓	2	6
Balamta, Majhgaun	12	✓	2	6
Aaptar, Rasuwa	12	✓	2	6
Total	60		10	30

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2017)

General sampling for questionnaire A requires that the participants must be selected reasonably from both literate and illiterate groups. Regarding this point, the sampling maintained the both literate and illiterate participants during the survey. Participatory Method was held in all the five major survey points in Khotang and Udayapur district.

2.4 Limitations: Time, access, area, methods and participants

The survey was conducted in five points of different villages, viz. Durchhim, Halesi, Ratanchha, Balamta, and Aanptar. Especially, it was very difficult to gather and find the people satisfying all criteria for the qualified participants for the collection of the

data. We used mainly four types of tools. However, there are other effective participatory tools like Cause and Effect Tree (a tool used to assist community leaders in thinking about the reasons why they use the language and what effects of the use of those languages on community members), Stakeholder Analysis (a tool used to help a small group of people to identify other stakeholders, categorize those stakeholders, select stakeholders to involve more and develop initial plans for involving them), Force field Analysis (a tool used to help a group who has a goal and wants to solve a problem to identify the forces working for and against the goal).

CHAPTER 3

DIALECTAL VARIATIONS

3.0 Outline

The main purpose of this chapter is to observe dialectal variations in Chamling. Basically two tools were used for this purpose. They include Wordlist Comparison, and Dialect Mapping. This chapter is organized into four sections. Section 3.1 deals with wordlist comparison in Chamling. Section 3.2 discusses the lexical and phonetic similarity in the Chamling language. In Section 3.3, we observe the global correspondences of the words in terms of lexical and phonetic level. Section 3.4 we discuss the dialect mapping in Chamling. In section 3.5, we summarize the findings of this chapter.

3.1 Wordlist comparison

The standardized wordlists of 210 words have been compared to estimate the degree of lexical and phonetic similarity among the Chamling speech forms the wordlists represent. In this section, we discuss the methodology employed in lexical similarity study and evaluation criteria for lexical similarity in percentage.

3.1.1 Methodology

The methodology comprises the collection of wordlists and tools used in the analysis of the wordlists. First, the standardized wordlist of 210 words were elicited in the survey points, namely, Hadunge, Halesi, Ratanchha, Balamta and Aanptar from the mother tongue speakers (grown up in the their locality, representing different sex, age and literacy), compiled them with phonetic transcriptions and cross-checked from other speakers from the same site (See Annex E for 210 wordlist). Secondly, the words from the wordlists were entered into the WordSurv (Wimbish, 1989), a tool primarily used to determine the genetic relationship of the languages or dialects. Thirdly, the words entered in the WordSurv were exported as WordSurv 6 XML file to Cog for the comparison of the words collected in the five survey points in terms of the lexical and phonetic similarity.

Cog is a tool for comparing languages using lexicostatistics and comparative linguistics procedures. It can be used to automate much of the process of comparing wordlists from different language varieties.

3.1.2 Evaluation criteria

According to Regmi (2013:63), 60% has been generally taken as a cutoff point for the evaluation of lexical similarity. However, the 60% threshold may not always be a strict cutoff point. Using such a method, the speech varieties having a lexical similarity less than 60% are considered as different languages. However, languages (or dialects) with around 60% or greater lexical similarity should be tested for intelligibility using another tool referred to as Recorded Text Test (RTT). The attitudes and the perceptions of the speakers are also important factors. Table 3.1 presents the evaluation criteria of the lexical similarity percentages among the wordlists.

Table 3.1: Evaluation criteria of the lexical similarity

	Lexical similarity (%)	Evaluation	Remarks
1.	60% similarity	A cutoff point/threshold for the evaluation	May not always be a strict cutoff point
2.	Less than 60% similarity	Different languages	
3.	60% or more similarity	Different languages or dialects of the same language	Intelligibility testing is required by using RTT
4.	Higher than 85% similarity	Speech varieties likely to be related dialects	
5.	Higher than 95% similarity	Same language	

3.2 Lexical and phonetic similarity

In this section, we compare and analyze the 210 wordlist using a computer software COG, a recently developed program for lexical and phonetic comparison between and among dialects and languages. Cog allows us to compare and analyze wordlists from different language varieties using an iterative approach. Using this program we can quickly make sense of the data and then more refine the wordlists and settings, improving the comparison results and the understanding of the varieties at each step.

In this section, we, first, present the lexical similarity in percentage among the survey points in the Chamling speech community and then phonetic similarities among the survey points.

3.2.1 Lexical similarity

Chamling presents different arrays of lexical similarity percentages among the survey points. Table 3.2 presents the lexical similarity in percentage among the survey points in the Chamling speech community in the Khotang and Udayapur districts.

Table 3.2: Lexical similarity among the key points of Chamling

	Hadunge	Halesi	Aanpatar	Balamta	Ratanchha
Hadunge	100%	99%	94%	76%	75%
Halesi	99%	100%	95%	75%	75%
Aanpatar	94%	95%	100%	96%	77%
Balamta	76%	75%	78%	100%	76%
Ratanchha	75%	75%	77%	76%	100%

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 3.2 shows that Balamta, the core area of Chamling, exhibits a significant degree (ranging from 75% to 78%) of lexical similarity with other survey points, i.e. Hadunge, Halesi, Aanpatar and Ratanchha. Of the 210 words, Balamta exhibits the highest similarity with Aanptar and the least similarity with Ratanchha and Halesi. Until intelligibility testing is carried out by using RTT, it is very difficult to say whether it is form of different language or a dialect.

3.2.2 Phonetic similarity

Chamling presents different ranges of phonetic similarity percentages among the survey points. Table 3.3 presents the phonetic similarity percentage among the survey points in the Chamling speech community.

Table 3.3: Phonetic similarity in the key points in the Chamling speech community (in percentage)

	Hadunge	Halesi	Aanpatar	Balamta	Ratanchha
Hadunge	100%	98%	95%	81%	78%
Halesi	98%	100%	96%	81%	79%
Aanpatar	95%	96%	100%	82%	79%
Balamta	81%	81%	78%	100%	79%
Ratanchha	78%	79%	79%	79%	100%

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 3.3 shows that as Balamta, the core area of Chamling, exhibits a significant degree (ranging from 78 % to 98 %) of phonetic similarity with other survey points, i.e. Hadunge, Halesi, Aanpatar and Ratanchha.

Figure 3.1: Similarities matrix in hierarchical dendrogram graphs

a) Lexical

b) Phonetic

Figure 3.1 (a-b) shows that there basically three speech varieties: a) Ratanchha b) Balamta and c) Aanptar including its subgroups Hadunge, an Halesi. The survey points Hadunge, Halesi and Aanptar share the closer lexical and phonetic similarity.

Similarly, the network graph lays out the language varieties, where similar varieties will tend to cluster together. This can be represented in the form of lexical and phonetic network graph in Figure 3.2 (a-b).

Figure 3.2: Similarity matrix network graph a) lexical and b) phonetic

a) Lexical

b) Phonetic

In a Figure 3.2 (a-b), the graph shows that the clusters of similar varieties and their connection. The speech community Hadunge, Halesi and Aanpatar seem to be closer whereas the Speech community Balamta and Ratanchha stand separately. This can be realized lexically and phonetically.

3.3 Global correspondences

The global correspondence displays all of the segments that occur in a particular syllable position across the wordlists from all the five survey points. Edges indicate that at least one correspondence has occurred between those two segments. The thickness of the edge indicates the number of correspondences.

Figure 3.3 presents an IPA consonant chart (column headers are place of articulation; rows are manner of articulation) in their onset position.

Figure 3.3: Global correspondences of Chamling phonemes in onset positions

This chart allows us to get a good sense of correspondences that occur across multiple variety pairs. Similarly, Figure 3.4 presents the corresponding of the different phonemes in their nucleus position.

Figure 3.4: Global correspondence of Chamling phonemes in nucleus positions

Figure 3.4 shows the vowels phonemes of Chamling in nucleus position of the syllables. The thickness of the edge indicates the number of correspondences.

3.4 Dialect mapping

The dialect mapping is one of the tools that helps the community members to think about and visualize the different varieties. The informants in group in each key point were asked to write on a separate sheet of paper the name of each village where Chamling is spoken and placed them on the floor to represent the geographical location. In common, the following name of the villages was recognized as Chamling language speaking areas: Hadunge, Halesi, Ratanchha, Balamta, Aanptar. Then they were asked to use the loops of string to show which villages spoke the same as others. But they told that there is no unintelligibility each other in their language.

3.5 Summary

In this chapter about the dialectal variation, we first assessed the levels of lexical and phonetic similarities among the forms of speech spoken in the survey points in the Chamling speech community. Across the survey points, there appear different ranges of lexical and phonetic similarities. Such similarity percentages clearly indicate that Chamling spoken in five survey points are mutually intelligible to each other. Being based on the Balamta, the core area of Chamling, exhibits a significant degree (ranging from 75% to 78%) of lexical similarity with other survey points, i.e. Hadunge, Halesi, Aanpatar and Ratanchha. Of the 210 words, Balamta exhibits the

highest similarity with Aanptar and the least similarity with Ratanhha and Halesi. The statistical data show that there is not much lexical variations among these five key points. Phonetically, Balamta, the core area of Chamling, exhibits a significant degree (ranging from 78% to 98%) of phonetic similarity with other survey points, i.e. Hadunge, Halesi, Aanptar and Ratanhha.

CHAPTER 4

DOMAINS OF LANGUAGE USE

4.0 Outline

This chapter explores the domains and patterns of language use in Chamling.¹ There are eleven sections in this chapter. Section 4.2 deals with the patterns of language use in general domains. In section 4.3, we deal with the patterns of language use at home. Section 4.4 looks at the patterns of language use by the children whereas in section 4.5 the patterns of language use by the community for marriage invitations are discussed. Section 4.6 deals with the patterns of language used to write minutes in community meetings. In section 4.7, we present the frequency of use of mother tongue in Chamling. Section 4.8 presents the frequency of use of the language of wider communication. In section 4.9, we examine the pattern of language use with the speakers of other languages visiting at home whereas in section 4.10 the preference of language for children's medium of instruction at primary level is discussed. Section 4.11 presents the summary of the findings of the chapter.

4.1 Patterns of language use in general domains

Pattern of language use is an interesting aspect of sociolinguistic study. It consists of various types of domains of language usage which are pertinent to daily activities of the human beings.

In this section, we examine the languages most frequently used by the Chamling speakers in terms of sex, age and literacy in different domains consisting of counting, singing, chanting, joking, shopping/marketing, storytelling, discussing/debate, praying, blessing, quarrelling, abusing (scolding/using taboo words), telling stories to children, singing at home, family gatherings and village meetings.

Table 4.1 presents the languages most frequently used by the Chamling speakers indifferent domains by sex.

¹ Domains of language use are generally referred to as the patterns of language use among the speakers of a language. More specifically, they are the contexts or situations in which a speaker makes a choice, in most of the cases, a conscious choice among his/her mother tongue, a language of wider communication and both or other languages. The main domains consist in community, home, business and education. The vitality of a language can be better examined by looking at the patterns of language use among the speakers in terms of sex, age and literacy.

Table 4.1: Languages most frequently used in different domains by sex (N=60)

Domains	Sex					
	Male (n=30)			Female (n=30)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Counting	2 (6.66%)	27 (90.00%)	1 (3.33%)	3 (10.00%)	25 (83.33%)	2 (6.66%)
Singing	2 (6.66%)	24 (80.00%)	4 (13.33%)	5 (16.67%)	20 (66.66%)	5 (16.67%)
Joking	2 (6.66%)	15 (50.00%)	13 (43.33%)	5 (13.33%)	11 (36.66%)	14 (46.66%)
Bargaining /marketing	4 (13.33%)	21 (70.00%)	5 (16.67%)	5 (16.67%)	24 (80.00%)	1 (3.33%)
Story telling	1 (3.33%)	16 (53.33%)	13 (43.33%)	2 (6.66%)	15 (50.00%)	13 (43.33%)
Discussing/ Debate	2 (6.67%)	16 (53.33%)	12 (40.00%)	3 (6.67%)	15 (50.00%)	12 (40.00%)
Praying	1 (3.33%)	18 (60.00%)	11 (36.66%)	2 (6.66%)	14 (46.66%)	14 (46.66%)
Quarrelling	2 (6.66%)	14 (46.66%)	14 (46.66%)	3 (6.67%)	15 (50.00%)	12 (40.00%)
Abusing/ Scolding	2 (6.66%)	16 (53.33%)	12 (43.33%)	4 (20.00%)	16 (53.33%)	10 (33.33%)
Telling stories to children	4 (13.33%)	16 (53.33%)	10 (33.33%)	6 (20.00%)	17 (56.67%)	7 (23.33%)
Singing at home	2 (6.66%)	20 (66.66%)	8 (26.66%)	3 (10.00%)	25 (83.33%)	2 (6.66%)
Family gatherings	2 (6.66%)	20 (66.66%)	8 (26.66%)	3 (6.67%)	23 (76.67%)	4 (20.00%)
Village meetings	4 (20.00%)	18 (36.67%)	8 (26.66%)	6 (20.00%)	13 (43.33%)	11 (36.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.1 shows the gender category of the participants, languages most frequently used in the different domains and the response of the participants. Nepali has now been a language of wider communication (LWC) in the Chamling community.

If we observe the domain of the counting, a majority of the male (90.00 %) and female (83.33%) participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling and Chamling and Nepali respectively. Similarly, the majority of the male (80.00%) and female (66.66%) reported that they most frequently use Nepali and 13.33% of males and 16.67% of females use Chamling and Nepali both respectively while singing. While joking, 70% of males and 36.66% of females use Nepali which is followed by Chamling and Nepali and Chamling respectively.

Regarding bargaining/ marketing, around 70% males and 80% females use Nepali which is followed by Chamling and Nepali and Chamling respectively.

A majority of the males (53.33%) and females (43.33%) were found to have used Nepali while telling the story. Regarding the discussion or debate, around 53.33% males and 50.00% females were found to have used Nepali.

For praying, the majority of males (60%) and females (46.66%) use Nepali. The majority of males (46.66%) and females (50%) were found in the command of Nepali while quarrelling. While scolding or abusing, almost the same 53% of males and females females reported that they use Nepali. When they tell the stories to their children, males (53.33%) and females (56.67%) were accustomed to tell in Nepali.

In the comparison to others, the participants told that they use less both Nepali and Chamling in the particular domains. Thus, domains of languages use clearly gives the picture of how Chamling speech community is shifting towards Nepali. Most of the domains as we discussed are out of the Chamling language *e.g.* counting, praying or singing.

Regarding the domain of family gatherings, a majority of the male (66.66%) and female (76.67%) participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling and Nepali and Chamling respectively.

And, in case of village meetings, a majority of the male (36.67%) and female (43.33%) participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling and Nepali, and Chamling respectively.

The patterns of language use in different domains are presented in the following figures.

Figure 4.1: Languages most frequently used by male in different domains

Figure 4.1 shows that in all the domains, Nepali is predominantly used in Chamling speech community. A majority of the participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali in the domains: counting, singing, joking, praying, singing at home, family gatherings and village meeting. As they reported that they use Chamling in the domains like telling stories to the children, family gatherings and village meetings less. But the percentage of the use of Chamling-Nepali is higher than that of the Chamling.

The patterns of language use by female in different domains may be more clearly further presented in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Languages most frequently used by female in different domains

Figure 4.2 shows that in all the domains like counting, singing, joking, praying, singing at home, family gatherings and village meeting, Nepali is predominantly used by female in Chamling community. However, the female use Nepali less than the male in all the domains in the Chamling community.

Table 4.2 presents the languages most frequently used by the Chamling speakers in different domains by age.

Table 4.2: Languages most frequently used in different domains by age

Domains	Age groups								
	A1(n=20)			A2 (n=20)			A3(n=20)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali + Chamling	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali + Chamling	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali + Chamling
Counting	-	18 (90%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	17 (85%)	1 (5%)	3 (15%)	16 (80%)	1 (5%)
Singing	1 (5%)	17 (85%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	13 (65%)	5 (25%)	3 (15%)	14 (70%)	3 (15%)
Joking	1 (5%)	12 (60%)	7 (35%)	2 (10%)	9 (45%)	9 (45%)	4 (20%)	5 (25%)	11 (55%)
Bargaining/ Shopping/ Marketing	1 (5%)	18 (90%)	1 (5%)	3 (15%)	15 (20%)	2 (10%)	5 (25%)	12 (60%)	3 (15%)
Story telling	-	15 (40%)	5	-	13 (65%)	7 (35%)	3 (15%)	3 (15%)	14 (70%)
Discussing/ Debate	-	17 (85%)	3 (15%)	1 (5%)	14 (70%)	8 (40%)	4 (20%)	7 (35%)	9 (45%)
Praying	-	15 (75%)	5 (25%)	1 (5%)	11 (55%)	8 (40%)	2 (10%)	5 (25%)	13 (65%)
Quarrelling	-	15 (75%)	5 (25%)	1 (5%)	11 (55%)	8 (40%)	4 (20%)	3 (15%)	13 (65%)
Abusing (scolding/using taboo words)	1 (5%)	15 (75%)	4 (5%)	2 (10%)	10 (40%)	8 (40%)	3 (15%)	7 (35%)	10 (50%)
Telling stories to children	1 (5%)	9 (45%)	3 (15%)	3 (15%)	10 (50%)	2 (10%)	6 (30%)	14 (70%)	9 (45%)
Singing at home	-	18 (90%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	15 (15%)	3 (5%)	3 (15%)	12 (60%)	5 (25%)
Family gatherings	1 (5%)	16 (80%)	3 (15%)	1 (5%)	16 (80%)	3 (10%)	3 (15%)	11 (55%)	6 (30%)
Village meetings	1 (5%)	17 (85%)	2 (10%)	3 (15%)	15 (55%)	2 (10%)	6 (30%)	12 (60%)	2 (10%)

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-59 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.2 shows that in almost all the domains of language use a large number of the speakers consisting of age ranging from 15 to 34 (A1) and age ranging from 35-59(A2) use Nepali. The percentage of the speakers of A1 is slightly greater than that of the A2. However, this percentage is significantly greater than that of A3. The percentage of the speakers of sixty and above using Nepali is smaller than that of the A1 and A2. In the same way, the percentage of the speakers using Chamling of the age ranging from 60 and above is greater than that of A1 and A2. In case of the speakers using both Chamling and Nepali, the percentage of the A2 speakers is slightly greater than that of A1 and A3. This clearly shows that Chamling are gradually shifting to the language of wider communication, Nepali. The patterns of language use by A1 age in different domains may be more explicitly presented in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Languages most frequently used by age group A1

Figure 4.3 shows the responses of the participants of the age group of A₁ in various domains of language use. The figure clearly shows that a majority of the participants in domains of counting, singing, joking, reported that they most frequently used Chamling-Nepali, which is followed by Chamling and Nepali respectively.

Regarding the domains of shopping, storytelling, discussing, praying, quarreling, scolding, telling stories to the children, singing at home, family gatherings, village meetings, a majority of the participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling-Nepali and Chamling respectively.

Figure 4.4: Languages most frequently used by age group A2

Figure 4.4 shows the responses of the participants of the age group of A₂ in various domains of language use. The figure clearly shows that a majority of the participants in domains of counting, singing, joking, discussing, scolding, singing at home, village meetings, reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling-Nepali and Chamling, respectively.

Regarding the domains of shopping, storytelling, praying, quarreling, scolding, telling stories to the children, a majority of the participants reported that they most frequently used Nepali, which is followed by Chamling-Nepali and Chamling, respectively.

Figure 4.5: Languages most frequently used by age group A3

Figure 4.5 shows the responses of the participants of the age group of A₃ in various domains of language use. The figure clearly shows that a majority of the participants in domains of counting, singing, telling stories to the children, singing at home, family gatherings, village meetings, reported that they most frequently used Nepali.

In the domains of joking, storytelling, discussing, abusing-scolding, praying, quarreling, a majority of the participants reported that they most frequently used Chamling-Nepali.

Table 4.3: Languages most frequently used in different domains by literacy

	Literacy					
	Literate (N=45)			Illiterate (N=15)		
Doamains	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali and Chamling	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali and Chamling
Counting	1 (2.22%)	42 (93.33%)	2 (4.44%)	4 (26.66%)	10 (66.66%)	1 (6.66%)
Singing	2 (4.44%)	36 (80%)	7 (9.37%)	5 (33.33%)	8 (53.33%)	2 (13.33%)
Joking	1 (2.22%)	24 (53.33%)	20 (44.44%)	6 (40.00%)	2 (13.33%)	7 (46.66%)
Bargaining/ Shopping/ Marketing	3 (6.66%)	38 (84.44%)	4 (8.88%)	6 (40.00%)	7 (21.42%)	2 (7.14%)
Story telling	-	25 (55.55%)	20 (44.44%)	3 (39.28%)	6 (40.00%)	6 (40.00%)
Discussing/ Debate	1 (2.22%)	29 (64.44%)	16 (35.55)	4 (26.66%)	3 (20.00%)	8 (7.14%)
Praying	-	18 (40.00%)	27 (60%)	3 (42.85%)	5 (50%)	7 (46.66%)
Quarrelling	1 (2.22%)	27 (60.00%)	17 (37.27%)	4 (26.66%)	2 (7.14%)	9 (7.14%)
Abusing (scolding/using taboo words)	2 (4.44%)	27 (60.00%)	16 (35.55)	4 (26.66%)	5 (33.33%)	6 (40.00%)
Telling stories to children	3 (6.66%)	29 (64.44%)	13 (6.25%)	7 (46.66%)	4 (26.66%)	4 (26.66%)
Singing at home	1 (2.22%)	37 (82.22%)	7 (15.55%)	4 (26.66%)	8 (53.33%)	3 (20.00%)
Family	1	18	8	4	7	4

gatherings	(2.22%)	(40.00%)	(17.77%)	(26.66%)	(46.66%)	(26.66%)
Village meetings	3 (6.66%)	29 (64.44%)	14 (31.11%)	7 (46.66%)	3 (20.00%)	5 (33.33%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.3 shows that majority of the participants in terms of literate and illiterate is shifting to wider communication, Nepali. This is because that the domains of language use indicate that they use mostly the Nepali language. However, in general, the percentage of the illiterate using Chamling is greater than that of using Chamling and Nepali in almost all the domains of language use. Interestingly, in the domains of counting and singing in general, singing at home no literate Chamling makes use of mother tongue whereas illiterate ones still, though in some degree, are using Chamling in these domains. This clearly shows that those who are literate are more open to shifting to Nepali in the Chamling community.

Figure 4.6: Literate and Illiterate Participants

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

Figure 4.6 shows that a majority of the participants (75%) are literate and a minority (25%) are illiterate group.

Figure 4.7 : Languages most frequently used in different domains by literate

Figure 4.7 shows that the literate participants use the Nepali language predominantly in almost all the domains like counting, singing, joking, bargaining/shopping/marketing, storytelling, discussing quarrelling, abusing or scolding, telling stories to the children, singing at home, family gatherings and village meetings. In the domain praying they show their preference for both language Chamling and Nepali.

4.2 Patterns of language use at home

Home is the place where domains of language use are found to be vibrant. In this subsection, we discuss the patterns of language use at home especially while talking about educational matters, social events and other family matters.

4.2.1 Patterns of language use at home while talking about education matters

Table 4.4 presents the languages most frequently used while talking about education matters like school, admission, studies, teacher with different family members by sex.

Table 4.4: Languages most frequently used with different family members by sex

(Talking about education matters (like school, admission, studies, teacher, etc.)

Domains	Sex					
	Male (30)			Female (30)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Grandfather	4 (13.33%)	15 (50.00%)	11 (36.66%)	9 (6.66%)	15 (50.00%)	6 (6.67%)
Grandmother	4 (13.33%)	16 (53.33%)	10 (33.33%)	7 (23.33%)	15 (50.00%)	8 (26.66%)
Father	5 (16.66%)	18 (60.66%)	7 (23.33%)	7 (23.33%)	20 (56.67%)	4 (13.33%)
Mother	6 (26.66%)	17 (56.67%)	7 (23.33%)	8 (26.66%)	19 (60.00%)	3 (18.00%)
Spouse	5 (16.66%)	21 (70.00%)	7 (23.33%)	7 (23.33%)	20 (30%)	3 (18.00%)
Children	2 (6.66%)	24 (80%)	4 (13.33%)	5 (16.66%)	21 (70.00%)	4 (13.33%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.4 shows that in all the domains the male respondents make use of Nepali more than that of their mother tongue in comparison to the female respondents in Chamling community. The domain of speaking with their children is supposed to be the greatest domain in all domains of which are used Nepali as wider communication. There is found almost the same percentage of the Chamling speakers in both sexes. The percentage shows that there is being loose of intergenerational transmission of Chamling language to the children.

Table 4.5 presents the languages most frequently used while talking about education matters like school, admission, studies, teacher with different family members by age.

Table 4.5: Languages most frequently used with different family members by age

(Talking about education matters (like school, admission, studies, teacher, etc.)

Domains	Age groups								
	A1			A2			A3		
	Chamling	Nepali	Nepali-Chamling	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Grandfather	1 (5%)	15 (75%)	4 (20%)	5 (35%)	10 (40%)	5 (15%)	7 (10%)	5 (40%)	8 (40%)
Grandmother	2 (10%)	12 (60%)	6 (30%)	3 (15%)	10 (40%)	7 (15%)	6 (30%)	8 (40%)	6 (30%)
Father	3 (15%)	11 (55%)	6 (30%)	4 (20%)	9 (45%)	7 (35%)	5 (30%)	8 (40%)	7 (35%)
Mother	3 (15%)	15 (75%)	2 (10%)	5 (40%)	15 (75%)	5 (5%)	6 (30%)	6 (30%)	8 (40%)
Spouse	2 (10%)	17 (85%)	1 (5%)	4 (20%)	7 (35%)	9 (20%)	6 (30%)	9 (45%)	5 (10%)
Children	-	10 (40%)	10 (40%)	2 (15%)	12 (60%)	6 (30%)	4 (20%)	6 (30%)	10 (40%)

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-59 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.5 shows that in all domains in general Chamling is used by a great number of the speakers. The speakers ranging from 15 to 34 (A1) speak Chamling less than the speakers ranging from 35-59 (A2) and 60 above (A3). While speaking with the spouse

and children in the domains mentioned above, the speakers are found to have been shifting slowly and gradually to Nepali.

Table 4.6 presents the languages most frequently used with different family members by literacy.

Table 4.6: Languages most frequently used with different family members by literacy

(Talking about education matters (like school, admission, studies, teacher, etc.)

Domains	Literacy					
	Literate (45)			Illiterate (15)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling -Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling -Nepali
Grandfather	6 (40.00%)	25 (55.55%)	14 (31.11%)	7 (46.66%)	5 (33.33%)	3 (20.00%)
Grandmother	4 (20%)	26 (40.62%)	15 (33.33%)	7 (46.66%)	5 (33.33%)	3 (20.00%)
Father	5 (11.11%)	35 (77.77%)	5 (11.11%)	7 (46.42%)	4 (26.66%)	4 (26.66%)
Mother	6 (40.00%)	33 (73.33%)	6 (40.00%)	8 (53.33%)	3 (20.00%)	4 (7.14%)
Spouse	5 (11.11%)	35 (77.77%)	5 (11.11%)	7 (46.66%)	3 (20.00%)	5 (33.33%)
Children	3 (6.66%)	40 (88.88%)	2 (4.44%)	5 (33.33%)	6 (40.00%)	4 (26.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.6 shows that literate speakers are using Nepali most frequently in almost all the domains while talking with family members about educational matters. In fact, those who are literate respondents they are found to literate predominantly in Nepali medium. Conversely, the illiterate people are found to be stronger in Chamling.

Around 40% of literate respondents use his/her mother tongue, *i.e.* Chamling while talking about educational matters with the children.

4.2.2 Patterns of language use at home while discussing social events and family matters

Table 4.7 presents the languages most frequently used at home while discussing social events and family matters.

Table 4.7: Languages most frequently used with different family members by sex

(Discussing social events and family matters (like festivals, election, ceremonies, marriage, savings, spending, *etc.*)

Domains	Sex					
	Male (30)			Female (30)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chaming-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Grandfather	4 (13.33%)	16 (53.33%)	10 (33.33%)	6 (20.00%)	9 (43.33%)	15 (50.00%)
Grandmother	5 (20.00%)	13 (50.00%)	12 (40.00%)	7 (23.33%)	10 (33.33%)	13 (16.66%)
Father	4 (13.33%)	15 (56.67%)	11 (43.33%)	6 (20.00%)	14 (46.66%)	10 (33.33%)
Mother	5 (33.33%)	16 (46.66%)	9 (30.00%)	7 (23.33%)	12 (40.00%)	11 (43.33%)
Spouse	3 (10.00%)	20 (66.66%)	7 (23.33%)	10 (43.33%)	16 (46.66%)	4 (13.33%)
Children	2 (6.66%)	22 (36.66%)	6 (20.00%)	4 (13.33%)	15 (53.33%)	11 (43.33%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.7 shows that in general the male speakers use Nepali more than those of female speakers. Although the range of speaking Chamling is higher than the use of Nepali, the speakers are shifting to Nepali. While talking with children, both male and female use Nepali more frequently than Chamling.

Table 4.8 presents the languages most frequently used at home while discussing social events and family matters by age.

Table 4.8: Languages most frequently used with different family members by age

(Discussing social events and family matters (like festivals, election, ceremonies, marriage, savings, spending, etc.)

Domains	Age groups								
	A1			A2			A3		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Grandfather	1 (15%)	14 (60%)	5 (5%)	2 (10%)	10 (40%)	8 (20%)	7 (30%)	1 (45%)	12 (5%)
Grandmother	2 (10%)	13 (75%)	5 (5%)	3 (20%)	7 (40%)	10 (5%)	7 (25%)	3 (50%)	10 (5%)
Father	2 (15%)	13 (50%)	5 (5%)	3 (10%)	9 (55%)	8 (5%)	5 (15%)	7 (50%)	8 (5%)
Mother	2 (20%)	13 (60%)	5 (10%)	3 (15%)	10 (65%)	7 (5%)	7 (10%)	5 (40%)	8 (10%)
Spouse	2 (25%)	15 (45%)	3 (10%)	4 (20%)	12 (60%)	4 (20%)	8 (15%)	8 (50%)	4 (5%)
Children	1 (30%)	14 (50%)	5 (15%)	2 (30%)	13 (35%)	5 (25%)	4 (45%)	9 (25%)	7 (5%)

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.8 shows that the A3 respondents in comparison to A1 and A2 use Nepali less frequently than Chamling and Nepali and Chamling. In the same way, while speaking

to children, while discussing social events and family matters, in comparison to A1 and A2 age groups, the A3 age groups use Nepali less frequently.

Table 4.9 presents the languages most frequently used at home while discussing social events and family matters by literacy.

Table 4.9: Languages most frequently used with different family members by literacy

(Discussing social events and family matters (like festivals, election, ceremonies, marriage, savings, spending, etc.)

Domains	Literacy					
	Literate (45)			Illiterate (15)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling -Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling -Nepali
Grandfather	5 (40.00%)	19 (42.22%)	21 (46.66%)	5 (33.33%)	6 (40.00%)	4 (26.66%)
Grandmother	5 (40.00%)	20 (44.44%)	20 (44.44%)	7 (46.66%)	3 (20.00%)	5 (33.33%)
Father	5 (40.00%)	26 (57.77%)	14 (31.11%)	5 (33.33%)	3 (20.00%)	7 (46.66%)
Mother	21 (46.66)	6 (13.33%)	3 (6.66%)	14 (93.33%)	11 (73.338%)	2 (7.14%)
Spouse	7 (15.55%)	31 (68.88%)	7 (15.55%)	6 (40.00%)	5 (33.33%)	4 (26.66%)
Children	2 (4.44%)	31 (68.88%)	12 (26.66%)	4 (26.66%)	6 (40.00%)	5 (33.33%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.9 shows that the majority of literate speakers were found to have used Nepali most frequently than those of the illiterate speakers while discussing social events and

family matters with the major family members. More strikingly, literate respondents are found to have been shifting towards Nepali, the language of wider communication, quite more while discussing social events and family matters. In the same way, the illiterate respondents responded that they used Nepali, the language of wider communication, but not as much the literate ones.

4.3 Patterns of language use by the children

There are three domains to examine the patterns of language used by the children: Playing with other children and talking with neighbors and at school. Table 4.13 presents the languages usually spoken by children.

Table 4.10: Languages usually spoken by children by sex

Domains	Sex					
	Male (n=30)			Female (n=30)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling- Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling- Nepali
Playing with other children	7 (23.33%)	14 (46.66%)	9 (30.00%)	8 (26.66%)	12 (40.00%)	10 (33.33%)
Talking with neighbors	2 (6.66%)	15 (50.00%)	13 (43.33%)	6 (23.33%)	10 (33.33%)	14 (46.66%)
At school	2 (6.66%)	21 (70.00%)	7 (23.33%)	3 (83.33%)	18 (60.00%)	9 (30.00%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.10 shows that that majority of the speakers pointed Nepali is much used in the three domains. This is because of the pocket area of Chamling speakers. It is claimed that non-Chamling also have access in Chamling language. Table 4.11 presents the languages usually spoken by children by age.

Table 4.11: Languages usually spoken by children by age

Domains	Age groups								
	A1			A2			A3		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali
Playing with other children	3 (15%)	9 (45%)	8 (40%)	5 (25%)	9 (45%)	6 (30%)	7 (35%)	8 (40%)	5 (20%)
Talking with neighbors	1 (5%)	11 (35%)	8 (40%)	2 (10%)	8 (40%)	9 (45%)	8 (40%)	2 (10%)	10 (50%)
At school	1 (5%)	15 (75%)	4 (20%)	2 (10%)	13 (65%)	5 (20%)	3 (15%)	10 (50%)	7 (35%)

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.11 shows that all the respondents of all age group say that Nepali is predominantly used by the children while playing with other children, talking with neighbors and at schools. As reported by the A3, the children are claimed to have spoken Chamling than those of the reports of the A2 and A1.

Table 4.12 presents the languages usually spoken by children by literacy.

Table 4.12: Languages usually spoken by children in different domains by literacy

Domains	Literacy					
	Literate (45)			Illiterate (15)		
	Chamling	Nepali	Chamling-Nepali	Chamling	Nepai	Chamling-Nepali
Playing with other children	11 (24.44%)	18 (40.00%)	16 (35.55%)	4 (26.66%)	8 (35.71%)	3 (20.00%)
Talking with neighbors	5 (11.11%)	30 (66.66%)	10 (22.22%)	3 (20.00%)	6 (40.00%)	6 (40.00%)
At school	3 (6.66%)	34 (75.55%)	9 (20.00%)	2 (13.33%)	6 (40.00%)	7 (46.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.12 shows that both literate and illiterate respondent said that the children use Nepali to the highest degree while playing with other children. Out of 45 literate responded reported that almost 75.55 % of their children speak Nepali at school and 40% use both Chamling and Nepali. On the other hand, of 15 illiterate correspondents replied that around 40% of their children speak Nepali at school and the rest percentage (40%) covers Chamling and Nepali both.

4.4 Patterns of language use by the community for marriage invitations

In Chamling communities the marriage invitations were confined to oral tradition. Nowadays, the invitation card is made in the written form with some cultural identity.

This domain also helps to examine the language vitality in Chamling community. Table 4.13 presents languages used for marriage invitations by the community by sex.

Table 4.13: Languages used for marriage invitations by the community by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Chamling	5 (20.00%)	7 (23.33%)	12 (20.00%)
Nepali	16 (53.33)	13 (50.00%)	29 (33.33%)
Chamling-Nepali	9 (43.33%)	10 (33.33%)	19 (31.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.13 shows 53.33 % of the male responded that they used Nepali for marriage invitations whereas 50 % of female used Nepali for the same purpose. Almost the same percentage of both sexes use Chamling for marriage invitations. While looking at the use of Nepali and Chamling, it is found males tend to use more than the female respondents. In fact, Chamling does not have a long tradition of writing system. As mentioned above, they invite their relatives orally on the occasion of marriage ceremony.

Table 4.14: Languages used for marriage invitations the community by age

Domains	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Chamling	3 (15.00%)	4 (20.00%)	5 (95%)	12 (20.00%)
Nepali	13 (65.00 %)	9 (45.00%)	7 (35.00)	39 (65.00%)
Chamling-Nepali	4 (20.00%)	7 (35.00%)	8 (40.00%)	19 (31.66%)

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.14: shows that majority of A1, *i.e.* 65 % use Nepali for marriage invitations. Of them, 20 respondents of A1 reported that they use 20 % Chamling and Nepali for the same purpose. Similarly, the majority of the A2 respondents use Nepali for the purpose of marriage invitations while only 45% of the respondents were found to have assembled with Chamling and Nepali for invitation card. In case of A3, 65% reported that they use Nepali for marriage invitations. Only 31% of the respondents were found to have followed Nepali and Chamling both for marriage invitations.

Table 4.15: Languages used for marriage invitations the community by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total(N=60)
	Literate (n=45)	Illiterate (n=15)	
Chamling	8 (17.77%)	4 (26.66%)	12 (20.00%)
Nepali	22	7	29

	(48.88%)	(46.66%)	(48.88%)
Chamling-Nepali	15 (33.33%)	4 (26.66%)	19 (831.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.15 shows that the majority of the literate, i.e. 82.48.88 % used Nepali for marriage invitations. Only 9.37 % of the literate make use of Both Nepali and Chamling for the same purpose. In the case of illiterate respondents, 48.00% use Nepali for marriage invitations. On the other hand, only 8.33% were found to have adopted Nepali and Chamling both for marriage invitations.

4.5 Patterns of language use in writing the minutes of the community meetings

Table 4.19 presents the languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by sex.

Table 4.16: Languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Chamling	-	-	-
Nepali	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	60 (100%)
Chamling-Nepali	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.16 shows that almost all respondents of both sexes use Nepali while writing minutes in community meetings. Almost all the female respondents (100%) use Nepali while writing minutes. Table 4.17 presents the languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by age.

Table 4.17: Languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by age

Domains	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Chamling	-	-	-	-
Nepali	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	60 (100%)
Chamling-Nepali	-	-	-	-

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.17 shows almost all the respondents of A1, A2 and A3 use Nepali to write minutes in community meetings in Chamling.

Table 4.18 presents the languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by literacy.

Table 4.18: Languages usually used to write minutes in community meetings by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total (N=60)
	Literate (n=45)	Illiterate (n=15)	
Chamling	45 (100%)	15 (100%)	60 (100%)
Chamling	-	-	-
Chamling-Nepali	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.18 shows, like by sex and age, irrespective of literacy; Nepali is overwhelmingly used to write minutes in community meetings in Chamling.

4.6 The frequency of use of mother tongue

The vitality of language is mapped out in terms of the frequency of the mother tongue in practical life. Table 4.19 presents the frequency of use of mother tongue by sex.

Table 4.19: The frequency of the use of mother tongue by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Everyday	9 (30.00%)	11 (36.66%)	20 (33.33%)
Rarely	9 (30.00%)	12 (40.00%)	21 (35.00%)
Never	12 (40.00%)	7 (23.33%)	19 (31.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.19 shows that the percentage of female using their mother tongue every day is greater than those of male respondents. However, the percentage of male using their mother tongue rarely is greater than that of female.

Table 4.20 presents the frequency of use of mother tongue by age.

Table 4.20 : The frequency of the use of mother tongue by age

	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Everyday	3 (15%)	6 (30%)	11 (55%)	22 (3.66%)
Rarely	4 (20%)	6 (30%)	4 (20%)	14 (23.33%)

Never	13 (65%)	8 (12.5)	5 (25%)	26 (43.33%)
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Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.20 shows that the percentage of A3 using the mother tongue every day is greater than those of A2 and A3 whereas the percentage of A2 using the mother tongue rarely is slightly greater than that of A1. The percentage of the respondents of A3 using the mother tongue rarely is lesser than by one-third of that of A1. The respondents belonging to A1 covers 65% who never use Chamling. This clearly shows that young generations are gradually shifting to Nepali, the language of wider communication, for whatsoever reasons. Table 4.21 presents the frequency of use of mother tongue by literacy.

Table 4.21: The frequency of the use of mother tongue by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total (N=60)
	Literate (n=45)	Illiterate (n=15)	
Everyday	13 (28.88%)	7 (46.66%)	20 (33.33%)
Rarely	15 (33.33%)	6 (40.00%)	21 (35.00%)
Never	17 (37.77%)	2 (13.33%)	19 (31.66%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.21 shows that the percentage of illiterate using the mother tongue every day is greater than that of literate. The percentage of illiterate who responded that they rarely used their mother tongue is smaller than those of literate respondents. Only 3.57% respondents responded that they never used their mother tongue.

4.7 The frequency of use of the language of wider communication

In Chamling community, in general, Nepali serves as the language of wider communication. Table 4.25 presents the frequency of the use of the language of wider communication.

Table 4.22: The frequency of the use of the language of wider communication by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Everyday	28 (93.33%)	26 (86.66%)	54 (90%)
Rarely	2 (6.66%)	4 (13.33)	6 (10%)
Never	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.22 shows except 6.6 % of the total male and 13.3% of the female all other respondents (both male and female) use Nepali everyday as the language of wider communication every day.

Table 4.23 presents the frequency of the use of the language of wider communication in Chamling community by age.

Table 4.23: The frequency of the use of the language of wider communication by age

Domains	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Everyday	19 (95%)	18 (90%)	17 (85%)	54 (90%)

Rarely	1 (5%)	2 (10%)	3 (15%)	6 (10%)
Never	-	-	-	-

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.23 shows that 95% of A1 use Nepali, the language of wider communication everyday whereas 5% of A1 use Nepali rarely. However, 90 % the respondents of A2 and 85% of A3 use Nepali as the language of wider communication.

Table 4.24 presents the frequency of the use of the language of wider communication in Chamling community by literacy.

Table 4.24: The frequency of the use of the language of wider communication by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total(N=60)
	Literate (n=45)	Illiterate (n=15)	
Everyday	32 (71.11%)	13 (86.66%)	54 (90%)
Rarely	4 (12.50%)	2 (7.15%)	6 (10%)
Never	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.24 shows that except 7.15% of illiterate and 12.50% of literate responded that Nepali is predominantly used as the language of wider communication. Of 45 male respondents, 71.11% responded that they used as the language of wider communication. Similarly 86.66 % of female respondents reported that that they use Nepali everyday as a wider communication.

4.8 Pattern of language use with the speakers of other languages visiting at home

We can evaluate the vitality of a language by examining the patterns of language use while the speakers of other languages visit the mother tongue speakers at home. In Chamling community, all the respondents irrespective of age, sex and literacy, Nepali is exclusively used while the speakers of other languages visit the mother tongue speakers at home.

Table 4.25 presents the language usually used when speakers of other languages visit at home by sex.

Table 4.25: The language usually used when speakers of other languages visit at home by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Nepali	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	60 (100%)
Chamling	-	-	
Nepali and Chamling	-	-	

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.25 shows that 100% male and female are use Nepali when the speakers of other languages visit the mother tongue speakers at home.

Table 4.26 presents the language usually used when speakers of other languages visit at home by age.

Table 4.26: The language usually used when speakers of other languages visit at home by age

Domains	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Nepali	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	60 (100%)

Chamling	-	-	-	
Nepali and Chamling	-	-	-	

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.26 shows that 100% respondents use Nepali when the speakers of other languages visit the mother tongue speakers at home.

Table 4.27: The language usually used when speakers of other languages visit at home by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total(N=60)
	Literate (n=32)	Illiterate (n=28)	
Nepali	32 (100%)	28 (100%)	60 (100%)
Chamling	-	-	-
Nepali and Chamling	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.27 shows that 100% respondents use Nepali when the speakers of other languages visit the mother tongue speakers at home.

4.9 Preference of language for children's medium of instruction at primary level

Generally, children gradually tend to go on shifting to the language of the medium of instruction if their mother tongue is not used in education especially at primary level.

Table 4.28 presents the preference of language for children's medium of instruction at primary level by sex.

Table 4.28: The preference of language for children's medium of instruction at primary level by sex

Domains	Sex		Total (N=60)
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	
Mother tongue	27 (90%)	28 (93.33%)	55 (91.66%)
Nepali	1 (3.12%)	1 (3.12%)	2 (3.34%)
English	2 (6.66)	1 (3.12%)	3 (5%)
Other	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.28 shows majority of both male and female responded that they prefer their mother tongue, *i.e.* Chamling, as the children's medium of instruction at primary level. In comparison to male, a slightly more percentage of female responded that they prefer Nepali as the children's medium of instruction at the primary level. There are also some respondents who prefer English as the medium of instruction for children at primary level. The preference of language for children's medium of instruction at primary level by sex can be presented in Figure 4.8.

Table 4.29 presents the preference of language children's medium of instruction at primary level by age.

Table 4.29: The preference of language children's medium of instruction at primary level by age

Domains	Age groups			Total(N=60)
	A1 (n=20)	A2(n=20)	A3(n=20)	
Mother tongue	16 (80%)	20 (100%)	20 (100%)	55 (91.66%)
Nepali	1 (5%)	-	-	2 (3.34%)
English	3 (15%)	-	-	3 (5%)
Other	-	-	-	-

A1= 15-34 years, A2=35-60 years, A3= 60 above

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.29 shows that, in terms of age, 80% of a total of 20 respondents of A1 prefer mother tongue for medium of instruction at primary level whereas 100% of A2 responded that they also prefer mother tongue for the medium of instruction for children at primary level. So is the case of the respondents from the age group A3. Those who prefer English as the medium of instruction belong to A1 age group. In totality, the table shows that in Chamling community there is a strong preference of the mother tongue as the medium of instruction for the children at primary level.

Table 4.30 presents the preference of language children's medium of instruction at primary level by literacy.

Table 4.30: The preference of language children's medium of instruction at primary level by literacy

Domains	Literacy		Total(N=60)
	Literate (n=45)	Illiterate (n=15)	
Mother tongue	41 (91.11%)	14 (93.33%)	55 (91.66%)
Nepali	1 (2.22%)	1 (6.66%)	2 (3.34%)
English	3 (6.66%)	-	3 (5%)
Other	-	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 4.30 shows the percentage of illiterate preferring their mother tongue as the medium of instruction at primary level is greater than that of literate. Moreover, only literate of 6.66% reported that they prefer English as the medium of instruction at primary level. It clearly shows that illiterate are more loyal to their mother tongue and they prefer their mother tongue to either Nepali or English as the medium of instruction at the primary level.

4.10 Summary

In this chapter we discussed the major domains of language use mapping out the language vitality in Chamling community. In the domains like counting, singing, joking, bargaining/ shopping/ marketing, storytelling, discussing/ debate, praying, quarrelling, abusing, telling stories to children, singing at home, family gatherings and

village meetings, Chamling speakers yield to have been shifting to Nepali, a wider communication slowly and gradually. In almost all the domains, a great number of the respondents of the age ranging from 15-34 and 35-59 years use Nepali more. The number of respondents of sixty and above using Nepali is smaller than that of the respondent's age ranging from 15- 34 and 35-59 years. The illiterate use Chamling more than Chamling and Nepali in almost all the domains of language use. Male respondents make use of Nepali more than that of their mother tongue in comparison to the female respondents in Chamling community. The domain of speaking with their children is supposed to be the greatest domain in all domains. There is found almost the same percentage of the Chamling speakers in both sexes. The percentage shows that there is being loose of intergenerational transmission of Chamling language to the children. A3 respondents in comparison to A1 and A2 use Nepali less frequently than Chamling and Nepali and Chamling. In the same way, while speaking to children while discussing social events and family matters, in comparison to A1 and A2 age groups, the A3 age groups use Nepali less frequently. The majority of literate speakers were found to have used Nepali most frequently than those of the illiterate speakers while discussing social events and family matters with the major family members. More strikingly, literate respondents are found to have been shifting towards Nepali, the language of wider communication, quite more while discussing social events and family matters. In the same way, the illiterate respondents responded that they used Nepali, the language of wider communication, but not as much the literate ones. Nepali is greatly used for marriage invitations and writing minutes in community meetings in Chamling community. The female use their mother tongue more frequently than the male. Those who are over sixty and illiterate use mother tongue more frequently than those below sixty and illiterate. Almost all those below 35 use Nepali, the language of wider communication every day. Nepali is exclusively used when the speakers of other languages visit Chamling at home. Majority of both sexes prefer their mother tongue as the children's medium of instruction at primary level. There are also some respondents who prefer English as the medium of instruction for children at primary level.

CHAPTER 5

MOTHER TONGUE PROFICIENCY AND MULTILINGUALISM, LANGUAGE VITALITY, MAINTENANCE AND ATTITUDES

5.0 Outline

This chapter maps out the mother tongue proficiency, multilingualism, language vitality, maintenance and attitudes in Chamling. It consists of five sections. Section 5.1 examines mother tongue proficiency and multilingualism. In section 5.2 we examine language vitality in Chamling. In section 5.3, we discuss language maintenance in Chamling. Section 5.4 looks at the attitudes of the Chamling community towards their language. In section 5.5, we summarize the findings of the chapter.

5.1 Mother tongue proficiency and multilingualism

There are found Chamling people shifting to multilingualism *via* bi-lingualism. If we see the degrees of the mother tongue proficiency or the language aspects like speaking, reading and writing, we find the tendencies moving towards multilingualism. Table 5.1 presents the mother tongue proficiency in speaking, reading and writing in Chamling.

Table 5.1: Mother tongue proficiency in speaking, reading and writing in Chamling**N=60**

Degrees	Speaking			Reading and writing		
	Male (n=30)	Female (n=30)	Total (N=60)	Male	Female	Total (N=60) (N=^)
Very well	7 (23.33%)	11 (36.66%)	18 (30.00%)	9 (30.00%)	3 (10.00%)	12 (20.00%)
Average	10 (33.33%)	10 (33.33%)	20 (33.33%)	10 (33.33%)	4 (13.33%)	14 (23.33%)
Only a little	7 (23.33%)	5 (16.66%)	12 (20.00%)	4 (13.33%)	9 (30.00%)	13 (21.66%)
Does not know	6 (20.00%)	4 (13.33%)	10 (16.66%)	7 (18.33%)	14 (36.67%)	21 (35.00%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.1 presents that 23.33 % male and 30 % female are found to be very well in speaking out of 60 participants. Almost the same percentage of the both male and female participants reported that they have equal access in the language average 33.33% speaking proficiency. Only a little is by 23.33% male and 16.66% female. Regarding the reading and writing, 30% male covers the degree of very well and 10 % by the female. Of the 60 participants, 20% of male and 16.66% were reported that they did not know the language at all in terms of the speaking proficiency. But on the other hand, 18.88 and 36.67% of female participants reported that they do not know reading and writing in the Chamling.

Basically, three tools were employed to examine multilingualism in Chamling. They include SLQ-A and SLQ-B. We present the results based on each tool as follows:

A. SLQ-A

Multilingualism is a common phenomenon in all the indigenous nationalities in Nepal.

There is tendency of language shift in Chamling community. Chamling people are found to have been converged to other languages like Nepali, Puma, Tilung and English as well as Hindi. This is because of the language contact. Table 5.3 shows tendency of the bilingualism/multilingualism in Chamling.

Table 5.3: Multilingualism in the Chamling community

(N= 60)

	Languages	No of speakers	Percentage
1	Chamling	39	65%
2	Nepali	60	100.00%
3	Puma	1	03.33%
4	English	37	1.66%
5	Hindi	12	60%

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.3 presents that around 93% of the Chamling participants speak their mother tongue. Of them, 100% Chamling participants speak Nepali. Around 1.67% Chamling participants were found to have access in Sherpa language. Other 10% of them could speak English and around 11.66% Chamling participants were able to speak Hindi language.

Figure 5.1: Multilingualism in the Chamling community

B. SLQ-B

To examine the situation of multilingualism in Chamling, a participatory tool was applied. The findings regarding the participatory method are as follows:

- a) There is no monolingual in the Chamling community.
- b) Children from Chamling community speak Chamling as mother tongue in the Chamling community.
- c) The children, young, middle aged and matured people, the leaders of the community, businessmen, the teachers and students are bilingual in both Chamling and Nepali.

5.2 Language vitality

Chamling community along with other indigenous communities is gradually shifting to Nepali. Most of the indigenous languages in hilly region are found to have transformed to

Nepali swiftly. Table 5.4 presents the data based on the responses related to language vitality provided by the informants in key points.¹

Table 5.4: Language vitality in key points in Chamling

PLACES	Do all your children speak your mother tongue?		Do young people speak your mother tongue as well as it ought to be spoken?		What language do most parents in this village usually speak with their children?	
	YES	No	YES	No	MT	NEPALI
HADUNGE	0	12	2	10	2	10
HALESI	0	12	1	11	2	10
RATANCHHA	3	9	3	9	3	9
BALAMTA	7	5	9	3	8	4
ANPTAR	0	12	2	10	0	12
TOTAL	10 (16.66 %)	50 (83.33%)	17 (28.33%)	43 (71.66%)	15 (25%)	45 (75%)

MT=Mother Tongue

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.4 shows the language vitality of the Chamling community which have been mapped out in five key points: Hadunge, Halesi, Ratanchha, Balamta and Anpatar. There were only three questions administered on the language consultants from each key point. When the first question was asked whether their children speak their mother tongue, 16.66% of them answered that their children speak it. The rest 83% children speak Nepali. The language vitality in Hadunge, Halesi and Anpatar is very low because the

¹ The responses were made to Qs (63-65) from SLQ A.

Chamling people of this area do not speak as they ought to. In response to the second question, they reported that their children do not speak the way they ought to speak it. When the participants were asked whether the young people in the Chamling community speak mother tongue as they ought to. But 28.33% of them answered they speak and 71.66% of them responded that they don't. When they were asked what language most parents in the village speak with their children, 25 % of them said that the parents speak their mother tongue with their children and 75% of them were shifting to Nepali. It shows the tendency of how language is shifting towards Nepali in Chamling community.

Figure 5.2 Speaking mother tongue by the children

The Figure 5.2 shows that the 16.66% of their children speak the mother tongue. The rest 83% children do speak Nepali. The language vitality in Hadunge, Halesi and Anptar is very low because the Chamling people of this area do not speak as they ought to.

Figure 5.3 Speaking mother tongue by the children

Figure 5.3 shows that 28.33% of the participants reported that the young people in the Chamling community speak mother tongue whereas 71.66% of them do not speak.

Figure 5.4 Speaking mother tongue by the children

The figure 5.5 shows that 25 % parents speak their mother tongue with their children and 75% of them were shifting to Nepali. It shows the tendency of how language is shifting towards Nepali in the Chamling community.

5.3 Language maintenance/ transmission

Table 5.5 presents the language maintenance/ transmission in Chamling where there is much influence of inter-cast or inter-ethnic marriage.

Table 5.5: Language maintenance in key points in Chamling

	Is there practice of inter-caste or inter-ethnic marriage in your village?		Do you like your children speaking mother tongue?	
	YES	NO	YES	NO
HADUNGE	10	2	11	1
HALESI	12	-	12	-
RATANCHHA	12	-	12	-
BALAMTA	11	1	10	1
ANPTAR	12	3	11	2
TOTAL	57 (95.00%)	3 (5.00%)	56 (93.33%)	4 (06.67%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

In response to the first question, we found that there is vibration of inter-caste or inter-ethnic marriage system. Of them, 95% reported that there is inter-caste and inter ethnic marriage in their community. When the language consultants were asked if intermarriage takes place which other language groups, they mostly answered that with other Rai Kiranti groups.

They were found to have got married with Puma, Wambule, Koyee and Magar. Since Kirati are of linguistic plurality, they cannot continue their mother tongue after they get married ones who are from other Kirati language communities. For instance, if someone from Tilung speaking community gets married with Chamling, she cannot communicate in her language with her spouse. This is one of the vibrant causes for disappearing Rai Kiranti languages. The sampled data show that only 5% reported that there is no inter-caste marriage system in their community.

When the informants were asked if they like their children learn/study their mother tongue, all the informants responded that they would like their children learn/study their mother tongue. Table 5.2 shows that 93.33% of the informants responded that there is intermarriage case in their community.

5.4 Language attitudes

Chamling people seem to be positive towards their mother tongue. The summary of the responses made by the participants on the subject matter of language attitude is presented in Table 5.6. Table present the distribution of the responses to what languages they love most.

Table 5.6: Distribution of the responses to what languages they love most

<i>What languages do they love the most?</i>	Male n=30	Female = 30	Total N=60
Chamling	29 (96.66%)	30 (100%)	100%
Nepali	1(3.33%)	-	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.6 shows that besides one male speaker all rest males prefer Chamling and love it most. Female speakers love their language most that covers 100% as can be seen in Table 5.6.

Table 5.8 presents the medium of instruction the participants prefer for their children to be taught at primary level. Mostly the participants seem to be positive towards their language to make the medium of instruction for their children in primary education.

Table 5.8: The medium of instruction you preferred for your children in primary education

	Male N=30	Female N=30
Mother tongue (Chamling)	27 (90.00%)	29 (96.66%)
Nepali	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
English	2 (6.66%)	-

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.8 shows that male (90%) and female (96.66%) are in the favor of the mother tongue for medium of instruction to teach children in primary level. Around 3.33% male and female only replied that they prefer Nepali as the medium of instruction at primary level. Some others were not in both; rather they prefer English which cover 6.66% by male.

(a) Feeling of the Chamling community while speaking their mother tongue

Table 5.9 presents the feelings of the consultants while speaking their mother tongue in the presence of the speaker of the dominant language.

Table 5.9: Feeling of the informants while speaking the mother tongue in the presence of the speakers of the dominant language

	When you speak your mother tongue in the presence of the speaker of the dominant language what do you feel	Male N=30	Female N=30	Total N=60
1	Prestigious	14 (46.67%)	13 (43.33%)	27 (45.00%)
2	Embarrassed	-	-	-
3	Neutral	16 (53.33%)	17 (56.67%)	33 (55.00%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.9 shows that around 46.67% male respondents feel prestigious when they speak their mother tongue in the presence of the speakers of the dominant language. The rest 53.33% were neutral in the response to this question. Around 43.33% female respondents told that they feel prestigious when they speak their mother tongue in the presence of the speakers of the dominant language. Of them, 55% of the female consultants responded that they have never had any problem because of being a native speaker of the Chamling language. No respondents reported that they feel embarrassed while speaking their mother tongue.

(b) Expectations from the future generations

Table 5.10 presents the response of the language consultants on the expectations from the future generations.

Table 5.10: Expectations of Language maintenance by future generations

Do you think children of the children at present will speak your language speak?	Male N=30	Female N=30
Will speak	18 (60.00%)	16 (53.53%)
Will not speak	04 (13.33%)	10 (33.34%)
Not Applicable(NA)	08 (26.67%)	04 (13.33%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

When the participants were asked whether their children would speak language in the future, around 60% male respondents replied that their children would speak it and 13.33% of them said that they would not. The rest male respondents did not respond at all. Around 53.53% females were sure of the future generations while other 33.34% female respondent replied that their children would not speak their mother tongue. Around 13.33% did not respond the question we asked for.

Table 5.11 presents that the response of how much they are aware of their language for teaching it to their children first.

Table 5.11: Responses to what language should their children speak first

What language should your children speak first?	Male N=30	Female N=30
Chamling	30 (100%)	30 (100%)

Source: Sociolinguistic Survey of Chamling (2016)

Table 5.11 shows 100% of the participants responded that their children should speak their mother tongue. It shows that the participants are aware of the language and their attitude towards language is positive.

5.6 Summary

In this chapter, we observed the mother tongue proficiency, bi/multilingualism, language vitality, language maintenance, and language attitudes in the Chamling community. If we observe the mother tongue proficiency, 23.33 % male and 30 % female are found to be very well in speaking out of 60 participants. Almost the same percentage of the both male and female participants reported that they have equal access in the language average 33.33% speaking proficiency. Only a little is by 23.33% male and 16.66% female. Regarding the reading and writing, 30% male covers the degree of very well and 10 % by the female. Of the 60 participants, 20% of male and 16.66% were reported that they didn't know the language at all in terms of the speaking proficiency. But on the other hand, 18.88 and 36.67% of female participants reported that they do not know reading and writing in the Chamling. Similarly if we look at the multilingualism then we find that Chamling speaking community shifting to multilingualism. Chamling community is found to have been shifting to Nepali, the language of the wider communication. Few of them were found that they could speak English and Hindi. Mostly the Chamling children do not speak their mother tongue as they ought to. All the participants reported that they felt 'good' if their children spoke their mother tongue and they reported that their children should speak mother tongue first rather than any other languages. No respondents reported that they feel embarrassed while speaking their mother tongue. Almost all the participants responded that they want their children study in their mother tongue at primary school. It shows that the participants are aware of the language and they are equally positive in their language.

CHAPTER 6

LANGUAGE RESOURCES AND LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

6.1 Outline

This chapter deals with language resources and language development in Chamling. It consists of four sections. Section 6.2 presents language resources in Chamling. In section 6.3, we discuss the dreams of the Chamling community for the development of their language. Section 6.4 presents the summary of the findings of the chapter.

6.2 Language resources

As the informants in key points reported that there are oral literatures available in Chamling which are *mundum* (the ritual and cultural text transformed orally from the elders to the descents since time immemorial), folk tales, songs and literatures. But there has been commenced the written literatures in Chamling. The oral ritual texts like *Mundum* is in the phase of documentation. For this, Kirat Rai Chamling Khambatim, an organization of Chamling people, has been working for the past ten years. Besides, the Chamling language is getting access in the FM Radio occasionally, namely Rupakot FM where the program is broadcast in the Chamling language. Similarly, there are magazines like *Sitimi*, *Michung*, *Dhiribung*, *Tuwachung*, in Chamling. Albums and music videos are also found to have released in the Chamling language. There can be found the contributions for their mother tongue Chamling named.

There are some of the organizations working to produce the Chamling language resources i.e. Chamling Chhamptim led by Tanka Bahadur Rai.

Table 6.1: Language resources*a) Literatures available in the Chamling language*

S.N.	Publication	Author	Publisher	Published year
01	Roduung Rai Chamlinga la Chuikham [Lets learn in the Chamling language] Grade 1	Chamling Rai Dhicung Khambatim, Kathmandu	Nepal GoN CDC, Bhaktapur	2001
02	Chamling la Chuikhama Iyu [Lets learn in the Chmling language] Grade 4	Kirat Rai Chamling Khambatim, Kathmandu, Nepal	Nepal GoN CDC, Bhaktapur	2064 B.S.
03	Chamling la chainkham [Lets learn in the Chmling language]Grade 5	Kirat Rai Chamling Khambatim, Kathmandu, Nepal		2065 B.S.
04	Chamling Chhachama Chhabla [Chamling Children Book)	Tanka Bahadur Rai	Uttar Kumar Rai	2062 B.S.
05	Dhinunglachi	Krishna Kumar Rai	Chamlingla shachham	2070 B.S.
06	Chamling la chainkham ik [Learning in the Chamling Language] Grade 1	Diwakar Dhungel and et al.		2072 B.S.
07	Chamaling la Chaikham Haka [Learning in the Chamling Language] Grade 2-5	Shanti Kumari Rai et al.	Nepal GoN CDC, Bhaktapur	2070 (1st edition)
08	Rodung Rilung	Bayansingh Rai	Author himself	2062 B.S.
09	Chamling-Nepali-English Dictionary	Prof. Dr. Novel Kishore Rai,	Kirat Rai Chamling Sabdakosh and Byakaran Niranman Mulsamiti	2001
10	Chmalingla-Iyungla laburkha [Chamling-Nepali Practical Dictionary]	Shanti Kumari Rai	ParshuRam Rai	2066 B.S.
11	Ila-Chamling Rai Sabda Sangraha[Chamling glossary]	B.B. Chamling Gangtok	Author himslef	1996
12	Chamling-Nepali Practical glossary	Gadulman Chamling	(NFDIN)	2065 B.S
13	Chamling Byakaran [Chamling Grammar]	Vishnu S. Rai	Kirat Rai Chamling Sabdakosh and Byakaran	2068 B.S.

			Niraman Mulsamiti	
14	Caming	Karen Ebert	LINCOM EUROPA	1997
15	Chamling-Nepali-English Dictionary	Prof. Dr. Novel Kishore Rai,	Kirat Rai Chamling Sabdakosh and Byakaran Niraman Mulsamiti	2001
16	Chamlingla dosomsa plisiye [How is Chaling spoken?]	Tanka Bahadur Rai	Krishna Kumar Rai	2060 B.S.
17	Chhamchi dimchi	Tanka Bahadur Rai	Tham Bahadur Chamling Rai	2051 B.S.
18	Pahilo Book (Primer Book)	Tilak Chamling	Milan Chamling	2056 B.S.
19	Michung (Collection of poems)	Shanti Kumari Rai	Gen Rai	2061 B.S.
20	imo bunga (Our flowers)	Tilak Chamling	Miyo Publication financed by NFDIN	2070 B.S.
21	Haikama (Earth)	Shanti Kumari Rai	Padma Rai	2061 B.S.
22	Anga bulim	Shanti Kumari Rai	Chamling Sachham Khambatim	2069 B.S.
23	aina mirungda (Don't say so]	Tanka Bahadur Rai	Chamlingla Shachham Khambatim	2067 B.S.
24	Anga dim hema anga kharu [Tanka Bahadur Rai	Chamling Sachham Kahmabtim	2069 B.S.
25	chmaling la plisiye [Lets speak in Chamling]	Chhila Rai	NFDIN	2073 B.S.

6.3 Language development

Language development is an incessant process. Hopes and plans of the speech community for the language development play vital role. Concerning this issue, the participants were asked what kind of hopes and plans they had thought for the mother tongue development. The responses of the participants are presented in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2: Hopes and plans for Chamling language

H o p e s	development and preservation of Chamling (<i>Mundum</i>)
	development of script (though there is debate on the Srijanga script);
	identification of Chamling phonemes;
	identification and development of Chamling literature;
	identification and development of Chamling folk music;
	identification and documentation of Chamling myths/ folklore
	identification and documentation of Chamling art
	getting support from National Foundation for Development of Indigenous Nationalities(NFDIN) for preserving Chamling language and culture and producing reading materials in Chamling;
	application of Chamling mother tongue at primary level education;
	Chamling language be aired <i>via</i> local media;
	scholarship support be provided by the government for the study of linguistics;
	discussion is carried out for making plans;
P l a n s	awareness program in the community be carried out;
	informal education be implemented;
	fund raising from the community, related organization, government agencies, etc;
	financial management for the Chamling language development and promotion.

Source: Sociolinguistic survey of Chamling (2016)

6.3.1 Appreciative inquiry

In the survey, a participatory tool known as appreciative inquiry was used in all five key points in Chamling. The main purpose of this survey was to gather information about the dreams and aspirations of the Chamling community members for the development of their language as well their culture. It was conducted in each point in a group of at least eight participants of different demographic categories of sex, education and educational status. The participants in each key point were asked to describe things that made them feel happy or proud of their language or culture.

They were asked to write down the ‘good things’ in a piece of paper and placed them serially in the floor. Then they were asked to, based on those good things in Chamling language and culture, say they “dreamed” about how they could make their language or culture even better. After having received their responses in the group they were advised to categorize the dreams from the easiest to the most difficult, specify which ones were most important and to choose a few to start on developing plans such as who else should be involved, what the first step should be and what resources they needed. Table 6.1 presents the summary of the responses to major queries in all seven key points in Chamling. 6.1 presents the summary of the responses to major queries in the points in Chamling.

Table 6.1: Summary of the findings from the appreciative inquiry in Chamling

Survey points	Good things that made Chamling feel happy or proud of their language	Dreams about how they could make their language even better	Most important dream to start on planning
AAPTAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ mother tongue of Chamling ▪ identity of Chamling ▪ legacy of <i>Mundumi</i> language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to prepare a grammar and a dictionary in Chamling ▪ to prepare textbooks for children in Chamling ▪ to have equal access to media ▪ to start mother tongue based education at primary level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to pressurize the local authorities to initiate FM and TV programs in Chamling ▪ to pressurize the government for high school to University level courses
BALAMTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ancestral language ▪ easy to communicate secrete matters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to prepare textbooks in Chamling ▪ to have any program in T.V ▪ to have Chamling teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to pressurize the local authorities to initiate FM and TV programs in Chamling ▪ to establish the University courses in Chamling language
RATANCHHA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ symbol of ethnic identity of ▪ easy to communicate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to prepare textbooks in Chamling ▪ to have any program in T.V ▪ to have Chamling teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to pressurize the local authorities to initiate FM and TV programs in Chamling ▪ to establish the University courses in Chamling language
HALESI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ symbol of ethnic identity of Chamling ▪ ancestral language ▪ easy to communicate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to start mother tongue based education at primary level ▪ to prepare textbooks in Chamling ▪ to use Chamling in government office 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to pressurize the local authorities to initiate FM and TV programs in Chamling
DURCHHIM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ symbol of ethnic identity of Chamling ▪ Chamling culture embodied in this language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to start mother tongue based education at primary level ▪ to prepare textbooks in Chamling ▪ to have any program in T.V 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to pressurize the local authorities to initiate FM and TV programs in Chamling

Table 6.1 summarizes the responses of how we could make queries to the participants in all the five key points. The first key point where the appreciative inquiry tool was used is Waku. In response to enumerate the good things that made them feel happy or proud of

their language and culture, the participants in group came to a conclusion that Chamling apart from being their mother tongue is an ancestral and a long established language in which many traits of their culture have been embodied since long. The group is very concerned about the status of their language. In response to express their dreams how they could make their language or culture even better, they concluded that they wanted to prepare the grammar and dictionary in their language. They shared their dreams that they need to have textbooks for their children at primary level. Apart from this, they would like to have equal access to the mass media like FM and TV. In other words, they would like to have any program in their language transmitted nationally or regionally or locally. They think that mass media is a very powerful means to motivate the people to think about the development of their language and culture. At the end they were asked to discuss what were the most important ‘dreams and aspirations’ which they would like to get realized. As it was not possible to do everything at a time, they were asked to choose most important among their dreams in order to start on developing plans on developing plans such as who else should be involved, what the first step should be and what resources they needed they concluded that they would like to make plans for transmission of the programs about Chamling language and culture through FM. For this they decided to held a meeting immediately in the village and appoint some people (both male and female) to pressurize the local bodies, members of parliament and their central committee to take immediate steps for this. The participants of other key points, namely, Hadunge, Halesi, Ratanchha and Aanpatar have almost the same aspirations as Balamta had.

6.3.2 Sociolinguistic questionnaire C

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C contains twenty-one questions. These questions were administered on the language activists and village heads. The main purpose of this questionnaire was to assess the language maintenance, language vitality and their attitudes towards their languages for language development.

All the participants reported there must be done something immediately to preserve and promote their language. The ways the participants reported for preserving and promoting their mother tongue in Chamling are:

- i) by documenting ritual language (classical language)

- ii) by publishing magazines or newspapers;
- iii) by producing dictionary and grammar in Chamling;
- iv) by encouraging Chamling community to produce literatures in various genres in their mother tongue;
- v) by writing and publishing textbooks and learning materials in Chamling;
- vi) by implementing Chamling in the medium of instruction at primary level, and
- vii) by using Chamling in administration
- vii) by approaching in the media

6.4 Summary

In this chapter, we outlined language resources, dreams and plans of the speech community for language development in Chamling. Chamling community is rich in oral literature: folk tales, songs and religious literature. They practice *Mundhum* as the religious norms. They have no access to mass media like television, FM radio, etc. Undoubtedly, Chamling is a preliterate language. They use the Devanagari script if they want to write in their language. There are a few organizations like Kirat Rai Chamling Khambatim devoted for the cultural, linguistic and educational development of the Chamling community. So far as the knowledge of the informants is concerned, they have neither grammar nor full-fledged dictionary and textbooks. In general, the Chamling community is aware that the language is very important for them. They think that Chamling is not only their mother tongue. Moreover, it is the symbol of ethnic identity. The language has embodied many aspects of their culture. They have very particular dreams and aspirations for the development of their language and culture.

They have dreams that preparing textbooks for children in Chamling, having equal access to media, starting mother tongue based education at primary level, establishing an organization for language development, having Chamling teachers and using Chamling language in government office. They have basically three most important “dreams” which they would like to get realized immediately. They include pressurizing the local authorities, starting program in T.V in Chamling, starting preparing textbooks in Chamling and beginning mother tongue based education at primary level. However,

they have not been systematically articulated in the plans All the village heads are convinced that they could preserve their mother tongue by making use of the language in the medium of instruction at primary level and a greater number of the village heads/ language activists would like to take immediate steps to make use of the language in administration.

CHAPTER 7

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Summary of findings

The main purpose of this study was to find out the sociolinguistic situation of Chamling, a Rai Kiranti language of Nepal. The survey includes a plenty of information about the possible dialectal variations and multilingualism, language vitality, language maintenance and language attitudes in Chamling. Moreover, the survey has also attempted to collect information about language resources, dreams and plans of the speech community for the development the Chamling language. The major findings of the survey are presented as follows:

- a) Chamling is one of the distinct Rai Kiranti languages having indigenous nationality (2002 NFDIN Act, No. 20, Section 2C).
- b) Chamling is spoken mainly in Hadunge, Halesi, Ratanchha of Khotang district and Aanptar and Balamta of Udayapur district in Nepal. However, they are found to have spread over in the districts like Taplejung, Panchthar, Ilam, Sankhuwasabha, Bhojpur, Panchthar, Morang, Sunsari, Jhapa and the Kathmandu valley.
- c) It is spoken by 76,800 Chamlings in eastern region of Nepal;
- d) This language is used in almost all domains of language use; however there is very few use of language in the domains like counting, praying and singing;
- e) Besing based on the Balamta, the core area of Chamling, exhibits a significant degree (ranging from 76% to 76%) of lexical similarity with other survey points, i.e. Hadunge, Halesi, Aanptar and Ratanchha. The study, on the basis of the comparison of standardized 210 wordlists by employing the computer program, COG, shows that there is more than 95% and less than 97% of lexical similarity among the key points in Chamling. With this fact we can argue that Chamling does not have any dialect as such.

- i) In the domains like counting, singing, joking, bargaining/ shopping/ marketing, storytelling, discussing/debate, praying, quarrelling, abusing, telling stories to children, singing at home, family gatherings and village meetings, Chamling speakers yield to have been shifting to Nepali, a wider communication slowly and gradually. In almost all the domains, a great number of the respondents of the age ranging from 15-34 and 35-59 years use Nepali more. The number of respondents of sixty and above using Nepali is smaller than that of the respondent's age ranging from 15-34 and 35-59 years. The illiterate use Chamling more than Chamling and Nepali in almost all the domains of language use;
- j) Male respondents make use of Nepali more than that of their mother tongue in comparison to the female respondents in Chamling community. The domain of speaking with their children is supposed to be the greatest domain in all domains. The percentage shows that there is being loose of intergenerational transmission of Chamling language to the children. A3 respondents in comparison to A1 and A2 use Nepali less frequently than Chamling and Nepali and Chamling.
- k) In the same way, while speaking to children while discussing social events and family matters, in comparison to A1 and A2 age groups, the A3 age groups use Nepali less frequently. The majority of literate speakers were found to have used Nepali most frequently than those of the illiterate speakers while discussing social events and family matters with the major family members.
- l) More strikingly, literate respondents are found to have been shifting towards Nepali, the language of wider communication, quite more while discussing social events and family matters. In the same way, the illiterate respondents responded that they used Nepali, the language of wider communication, but not as much the literate ones. Nepali is greatly used for marriage invitations and writing minutes in community meetings in Chamling community.

- m) The female use their mother tongue more frequently than the male. Those who are over sixty and illiterate use mother tongue more frequently than those below sixty and illiterate. Almost all those below 35 use Nepali, the language of wider communication every day. Nepali is exclusively used when the speakers of other languages visit Chamling at home. Majority of both sexes prefer their mother tongue as the children's medium of instruction at primary level. There are also some respondents who prefer English as the medium of instruction for children at primary level.
- n) Similarly, the inter-caste or inter-ethnic marriage system is also one of the causes of language shift. They were found to have got married with Puma, Tilung, Kulung, Wambule and Chheri-Brahman.
- q) Chamling community is rich in oral literature: folk tales, songs and religious literature. They practice *Mundhum* as the religious norms. They have no access to mass media like television, FM radio, etc.
- r) In general, the Chamling community is aware that the language is very important for them. They think that Chamling is not only their mother tongue. Moreover, it is the symbol of ethnic identity. The language has embodied many aspects of their culture. They have very particular dreams and aspirations for the development of their language and culture.
- s) They have dreams that preparing textbooks for children in Chamling, having equal access to media, starting mother tongue based education at primary level, establishing an organization for language development, having Chamling teachers and using Chamling language in government office. They have basically three most important “dreams” which they would like to get realized immediately. They include pressurizing the local authorities, starting program in T.V in Chamling, starting preparing textbooks in Chamling and beginning mother tongue based education at primary level. However, they have not been systematically articulated in the plans All the village heads are convinced that they could preserve their mother tongue by making use of the language in the medium of instruction

at primary level and a greater number of the village heads/language activists would like to take immediate steps to make use of the language in administration.

7.2 Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations are surfaced for the promotion and development of the Chamling language:

- a) As Chamling children face difficulties in basic education because of their unfamiliarity with the vernacular and textbooks in Nepali as well as the Interim Constitution of Nepal has to guarantee the right of mother tongue based multilingual education;
- b) Textbooks should be developed in such a way that they embody the local needs and local settings;
- c) By means of non-formal education in their mother tongue, the literacy classes must be conducted to uplift those illiterate;
- d) The government should immediately address the efforts and grievances of the Chamling community;
- e) A detailed language documentation project is essential to preserve, promote and develop their language and culture in which life crucial knowledge is embodied from time immemorial;
- f) Immediately grammar and dictionary should be written and compiled and the folklore, *Mundhum* must be documented;
- g) Unless the domains of use of language are broadened the language cannot be preserved. The Chamling community should be made aware of the importance of the use of their mother tongue and encouraged to transmit their mother tongue to the younger generations through advocacy.
- h) Non-formal education programs should be carried out in the mother tongue preparing the reading materials;
- i) Specific language development programs such as developing orthography, compiling bilingual and monolingual dictionaries and writing grammars should be immediately launched;

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Annexes

Annex A: Word lists

अनुसन्धाता (हरू) को नाम: मिति:.....

(१).....

(२).....

(३).....

(४)

(५)

भाषासूचक (हरू) को नाम:

(१).....

(२).....

(३).....

(४)

(५)

स्थान :

जिल्ला..... गाविस/नगरपालिका: वडा नं:.....

गाउँ/टोल:.....

भाषाको नाम: अन्तर्वार्ताको माध्यमभाषा:

S.N.	English	Nepai	Hadunge	Halesi	Ratanchha	Balamta	Aaptar
1.	body	शरीर	<i>bulim</i>	<i>bulim</i>	<i>ram</i>	<i>bulim</i>	<i>dziu</i>
2.	head	टाउको	<i>tak^hlo</i>	<i>tak^hlo</i>	<i>tak^hlo</i>	<i>tak^hlo</i>	<i>tak^hlo</i>
3.	hair	कपाल	<i>tō</i>	<i>tō</i>	<i>tamse</i>	<i>tō</i>	<i>tō</i>
4.	face	अनुहार	<i>ηai</i>	<i>ηai</i>	<i>ηai</i>	<i>ηai</i>	<i>ηai</i>
5.	eye	आँखा	<i>mitsuη</i>	<i>mitsuη</i>	<i>mai</i>	<i>mitsuη</i>	<i>mitsuη</i>
6.	ear	कान	<i>nabro</i>	<i>nabro</i>	<i>nabro</i>	<i>nabro</i>	<i>nabro</i>
7.	nose	नाक	<i>nadipuη</i>	<i>nadipuη</i>	<i>natipa</i>	<i>nadipuη</i>	<i>nadipuη</i>
8.	mouth	मुख	<i>djo</i>	<i>djo</i>	<i>djo</i>	<i>djo</i>	<i>djo</i>
9.	teeth	दाँत	<i>kiη</i>	<i>kiη</i>	<i>kuη</i>	<i>kiη</i>	<i>kiη</i>
10.	tongue	जिब्रो	<i>lem</i>	<i>lem</i>	<i>ljam</i>	<i>lem</i>	<i>lem</i>
11.	breast	स्तन	<i>sembu</i>	<i>sembu</i>	<i>pamtsuη</i>	<i>sembu</i>	<i>sembu</i>
12.	belly	पेट	<i>k^hori</i>	<i>k^hori</i>	<i>k^hari</i>	<i>k^hori</i>	<i>k^hori</i>
13.	arm/ hand	हात	<i>tsj^hu</i>	<i>tsj^hu</i>	<i>ts^hu</i>	<i>tsj^hu</i>	<i>tsj^hu</i>
14.	elbow	कुइनो	<i>ts^hilima</i>	<i>ts^hilima</i>	<i>ts^hilima</i>	<i>ts^hilima</i>	<i>ts^hilima</i>
15.	palm	हत्केला	<i>hepts^howa</i>	<i>hepts^howa</i>	<i>ts^hulapa</i>	<i>hepts^howa</i>	<i>hepts^how</i>
16.	finger	आँला	<i>amla</i>	<i>amla</i>	<i>ts^husja</i>	<i>amla</i>	<i>amla</i>
17.	fingernail	नङ	<i>toηli</i>	<i>toηli</i>	<i>tuηlima</i>	<i>toηli</i>	<i>toηli</i>
18.	leg	खुट्टा	<i>p^hilu</i>	<i>p^hilu</i>	<i>p^hili</i>	<i>p^hilu</i>	<i>p^hilu</i>
19.	skin	छाला	<i>bok^him</i>	<i>bok^him</i>	<i>fuljapa</i>	<i>bok^him</i>	<i>bok^him</i>
20.	bone	हाड	<i>saruwa</i>	<i>saruwa</i>	<i>saruwa</i>	<i>saruwa</i>	<i>saruwa</i>
21.	heart	मुटु	<i>sembutsuη</i>	<i>sembutsu η</i>	<i>hikudima</i>	<i>sembutsuη</i>	<i>sembutsuη</i>
22.	blood	रगत	<i>hi</i>	<i>hi</i>	<i>hi</i>	<i>hi</i>	<i>hi</i>
23.	urine	पिसाब	<i>ts^harde</i>	<i>ts^harde</i>	<i>ts^hjarapa</i>	<i>ts^harde</i>	<i>ts^harde</i>
24.	feces	दिसा	<i>k^hli</i>	<i>k^hli</i>	<i>k^hi</i>	<i>k^hli</i>	<i>k^hli</i>
25.	village	गाउँ	<i>tuηma</i>	<i>tuηma</i>	<i>tuηma</i>	<i>tuηma</i>	<i>tuηma</i>
26.	house	घर	<i>k^him</i>	<i>k^him</i>	<i>k^him</i>	<i>k^him</i>	<i>k^him</i>
27.	roof	छानो	<i>lebd^hero</i>	<i>lebd^hero</i>	<i>k^hamba</i>	<i>lebd^hero</i>	<i>lebd^hero</i>
28.	door	ढोका	<i>laptik^ho</i>	<i>laptik^ho</i>	<i>laptik^ha</i>	<i>laptik^ho</i>	<i>laptik^ho</i>
29.	firewood	दाउरा	<i>suη</i>	<i>suη</i>	<i>suη</i>	<i>suη</i>	<i>suη</i>
30.	broom	कुचो	<i>jets^habi</i>	<i>jets^habi</i>	<i>ja^hts^habi</i>	<i>jets^habi</i>	<i>jets^habi</i>
31.	mortar	सिलौटो	<i>g^huruηtina</i>	<i>g^huruηtin a</i>	<i>jumaluη</i>	<i>g^huruηtina</i>	<i>g^huruηtina</i>
32.	pestle	लोहोरो	<i>g^huruηma</i>	<i>g^huruηma</i>	<i>jumakuluη</i>	<i>g^huruηma</i>	<i>g^huruηma</i>
33.	hammer	हथौडा	<i>fiat^houda</i>	<i>fiat^houda</i>	<i>diluηk^hjakka</i>	<i>fiat^houda</i>	<i>fiat^houda</i>
34.	knife	चक्कु	<i>tsakku</i>	<i>tsakku</i>	<i>ts^hibak^ha</i>	<i>tsakku</i>	<i>tsakku</i>
35.	axe	बञ्चरो	<i>b^haiti</i>	<i>b^haiti</i>	<i>b^hjati</i>	<i>b^haiti</i>	<i>b^haiti</i>
36.	rope	डोरी	<i>ruk^hja</i>	<i>ruk^hja</i>	<i>ri</i>	<i>ruk^hja</i>	<i>ruk^hja</i>

37.	thread	धागो	<i>ri</i>	<i>ri</i>	<i>ri</i>	<i>ri</i>	<i>ri</i>
38.	needle	सियो	<i>ts^hutsui</i>	<i>ts^hutsui</i>	<i>ts^hitsai</i>	<i>ts^hutsui</i>	<i>ts^hutsui</i>
39.	cloth	लुगा (कपडा)	<i>tuĩ</i>	<i>tuĩ</i>	<i>ʈai</i>	<i>tuĩ</i>	<i>tuĩ</i>
40.	ring	औँठी	<i>ts^hikurma</i>	<i>ts^hikurma</i>	<i>ts^hikurma</i>	<i>ts^hikurma</i>	<i>ts^hikurma</i>
41.	sun	घाम	<i>nam</i>	<i>nam</i>	<i>nam</i>	<i>nam</i>	<i>nam</i>
42.	moon	चन्द्रमा	<i>lakane</i>	<i>lakane</i>	<i>lakane</i>	<i>lakane</i>	<i>lakane</i>
43.	sky	आकाश	<i>ninamma</i>	<i>ninamma</i>	<i>ninam</i>	<i>ninamma</i>	<i>ninamma</i>
44.	star	तारा	<i>putipa</i>	<i>putipa</i>	<i>pitipa</i>	<i>putipa</i>	<i>putipa</i>
45.	rain	वर्षा	<i>waq^hamma</i>	<i>waq^ham</i>	<i>waq^ha</i>	<i>waq^hamma</i>	<i>waq^hamma</i>
46.	water	पानी	<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i>
47.	river	नदी	<i>ts^hiwa</i>	<i>ts^hiwa</i>	<i>ɟawa</i>	<i>ts^hiwa</i>	<i>ts^hiwa</i>
48.	cloud	बादल	<i>mõmpa</i>	<i>mõmpa</i>	<i>mɔmijapa</i>	<i>mõmpa</i>	<i>badɔl</i>
49.	lightening	बिजुली चम्कनु	-	<i>bidzulitsa mkemu</i>	<i>naptsibu</i>	-	-
50.	rainbow	इन्द्रेणी	<i>nakima</i>	<i>nakima</i>	<i>nakima</i>	<i>nakima</i>	<i>nakima</i>
51.	wind	बतास	<i>fiu</i>	<i>fiu</i>	<i>fiui</i>	<i>fiu</i>	<i>fiu</i>
52.	stone	ढुङ्गा	<i>luŋto</i>	<i>luŋto</i>	<i>luŋto</i>	<i>luŋto</i>	<i>luŋto</i>
53.	path	बाटो	<i>lam</i>	<i>lam</i>	<i>lam</i>	<i>lam</i>	<i>lam</i>
54.	sand	बालुवा	<i>p^hrelɔluŋ</i>	<i>p^hrelɔluŋ</i>	<i>sjampuik^ha</i>	<i>p^hrelɔluŋ</i>	<i>balwa</i>
55.	fire	आगो	<i>mi</i>	<i>mi</i>	<i>mi</i>	<i>mi</i>	<i>mi</i>
56.	smoke	धुवाँ	<i>mik^hu</i>	<i>mik^hu</i>	<i>misam</i>	<i>mik^hu</i>	<i>mik^hu</i>
57.	ash	खरानी	<i>mud^hima</i>	<i>mud^hima</i>	<i>mud^hima</i>	<i>mud^hima</i>	<i>mud^hima</i>
58.	mud	माटो	<i>bok^ha</i>	<i>bok^ha</i>	<i>bakk^ha</i>	<i>bok^ha</i>	<i>bok^ha</i>
59.	dust	धुलो	<i>ri:</i>	<i>ri:</i>	<i>bakk^haluŋ</i>	<i>ri:</i>	<i>ri:</i>
60.	gold	सुन	<i>umnima</i>	<i>umnima</i>	<i>hipatimma</i>	<i>umnima</i>	<i>umnima</i>
61.	tree	रूख	<i>suŋpa</i>	<i>suŋpa</i>	<i>suŋpawa</i>	<i>suŋpa</i>	<i>suŋpa</i>
62.	leaf	पात	<i>labo</i>	<i>labo</i>	<i>labo</i>	<i>labo</i>	<i>labo</i>
63.	root	जरा	<i>umb^har</i>	<i>umb^har</i>	<i>b^hjar</i>	<i>umb^har</i>	<i>umb^har</i>
64.	thorn	काँडो	<i>tuŋk^hra</i>	<i>tuŋk^hra</i>	<i>tuŋk^huwa</i>	<i>tuŋk^hra</i>	<i>tuŋk^hra</i>
65.	flower	फूल	<i>buŋa</i>	<i>buŋa</i>	<i>bawa</i>	<i>buŋa</i>	<i>buŋa</i>
66.	fruit	फलफूल	<i>suŋseluŋse</i>	<i>suŋseluŋse</i>	<i>suŋseluŋse</i>	<i>suŋseluŋse</i>	<i>suŋseluŋse</i>
67.	mango	आँप	<i>ãp</i>	<i>ãp</i>	<i>ãp</i>	<i>ãp</i>	<i>ãp</i>
68.	banana	केरा	<i>ŋasi</i>	<i>ŋasi</i>	<i>ŋasi</i>	<i>ŋasi</i>	<i>ŋasi</i>
69.	wheat(husk ed)	गहुँ	<i>ts^hambets^ha</i>	<i>ts^hambets^ha</i>	<i>ts^hambets^ha</i>	<i>ts^hambets^ha</i>	<i>gɔhũ</i>
70.	barley	जौ	<i>tsuŋ</i>	<i>tsuŋ</i>	<i>tsuŋ</i>	<i>tsuŋ</i>	<i>tsuŋ</i>
71.	rice (husked)	चामल	<i>tsaruŋ</i>	<i>tsaruŋ</i>	<i>tsaruŋ</i>	<i>tsaruŋ</i>	<i>tsaruŋ</i>
72.	potato	आलु	<i>bok^hi</i>	<i>bok^hi</i>	<i>bok^hi</i>	<i>bok^hi</i>	<i>bok^hi</i>
73.	eggplant	भण्टा	<i>b^hok^hatsa</i>	<i>b^hok^hatsa</i>	<i>b^hok^hatsa</i>	<i>b^hok^hatsa</i>	<i>b^hok^hatsa</i>
74.	groundnut	बदाम	<i>badɔm</i>	<i>badɔm</i>	<i>badɔm</i>	<i>badɔm</i>	<i>badɔm</i>

75.	chili	खुर्सीनी	<i>birosi</i>	<i>birosi</i>	<i>birosi</i>	<i>birosi</i>	<i>birosi</i>
76.	turmeric	बेसार	<i>fiardi</i>	<i>fiardi</i>	<i>fiardi</i>	<i>fiardi</i>	<i>fiardi</i>
77.	garlic	लसुन	<i>numbasa</i>	<i>numbasa</i>	<i>numbasa</i>	<i>numbasa</i>	<i>numbasa</i>
78.	onion	प्याज	<i>pjadz</i>	<i>pjadz</i>	<i>pjadz</i>	<i>pjadz</i>	<i>pjadz</i>
79.	cauliflower	काउली	<i>kauli</i>	<i>kauli</i>	<i>kauli</i>	<i>kauli</i>	<i>kauli</i>
80.	tomato	गोलभेंडा	<i>belouti</i>	<i>belouti</i>	<i>belouti</i>	<i>belouti</i>	<i>belouti</i>
81.	cabbage	बन्दा	<i>bandakopi</i>	<i>bandakopi</i>	<i>bandakopi</i>	<i>bandakopi</i>	<i>bandakopi</i>
82.	oil	तेल	<i>beli</i>	<i>beli</i>	<i>beli</i>	<i>beli</i>	<i>beli</i>
83.	salt	नुन	<i>rum</i>	<i>rum</i>	<i>rum</i>	<i>rum</i>	<i>rum</i>
84.	meat	मासु	<i>sa</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>sa</i>
85.	fat (of meat)	बोसो	<i>umts^hui</i>	<i>umts^hui</i>	<i>umts^hui</i>	<i>umts^hui</i>	<i>umts^hui</i>
86.	fish	माछा	<i>ηasa</i>	<i>ηasa</i>	<i>ηasa</i>	<i>ηasa</i>	<i>ηasa</i>
87.	chicken	चल्ला	<i>wats^hja</i>	<i>wats^hja</i>	<i>wats^hja</i>	<i>wats^hja</i>	<i>wats^hja</i>
88.	egg	अण्डा	<i>piupa</i>	<i>piupa</i>	<i>piupa</i>	<i>piupa</i>	<i>piupa</i>
89.	cow	गाई	<i>māisi</i>	<i>māisi</i>	<i>māisi</i>	<i>māisi</i>	<i>māisi</i>
90.	buffalo	भैंसी	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>
91.	milk	दुध	<i>dūt</i>	<i>dūt</i>	<i>dūt</i>	<i>dūt</i>	<i>dūt</i>
92.	horns	सिङ	<i>siŋ</i>	<i>siŋ</i>	<i>siŋ</i>	<i>siŋ</i>	<i>siŋ</i>
93.	tail	पुच्छर	<i>meri</i>	<i>meri</i>	<i>meri</i>	<i>meri</i>	<i>meri</i>
94.	goat	बाख्रो	<i>lamkat^hima</i>	<i>lamkat^hima</i>	<i>lamkat^hima</i>	<i>lamkat^hima</i>	<i>lamkat^hima</i>
95.	dog	कुकुर	<i>k^hlipa</i>	<i>k^hlipa</i>	<i>k^hlipa</i>	<i>k^hlipa</i>	<i>k^hlipa</i>
96.	snake	सर्प	<i>puts^ho</i>	<i>puts^ho</i>	<i>puts^ho</i>	<i>puts^ho</i>	<i>puts^ho</i>
97.	monkey	बाँदर	<i>nuĩ</i>	<i>nuĩ</i>	<i>nuĩ</i>	<i>nuĩ</i>	<i>nuĩ</i>
98.	mosquito	लामखुट्टे	<i>tuŋkama</i>	<i>tuŋkama</i>	<i>tuŋkama</i>	<i>tuŋkama</i>	<i>tuŋkama</i>
99.	ant	कमिला	<i>tsikarepa</i>	<i>tsikarepa</i>	<i>tsikarepa</i>	<i>tsikarepa</i>	<i>tsikarepa</i>
100.	spider	माकुरो	<i>wakurma</i>	<i>wakurma</i>	<i>wakurma</i>	<i>wakurma</i>	<i>wakurma</i>
101.	name	नाम	<i>nuŋ</i>	<i>nuŋ</i>	<i>nuŋ</i>	<i>nuŋ</i>	<i>nuŋ</i>
102.	man	मान्छे	<i>mina</i>	<i>mina</i>	<i>mina</i>	<i>mina</i>	<i>mina</i>
103.	woman	आइमाई	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>
104.	child	बच्चा	<i>jats^ha</i>	<i>jats^ha</i>	<i>jats^ha</i>	<i>jats^ha</i>	<i>jats^ha</i>
105.	father	बाबा	<i>papa</i>	<i>papa</i>	<i>papa</i>	<i>papa</i>	<i>papa</i>
106.	mother	आमा	<i>mama</i>	<i>mama</i>	<i>mama</i>	<i>mama</i>	<i>mama</i>
107.	older brother	दाजु	<i>buwa</i>	<i>buwa</i>	<i>buwa</i>	<i>buwa</i>	<i>buwa</i>
108.	younger brother	भाइ	<i>nits^ho</i>	<i>nits^ho</i>	<i>nits^ho</i>	<i>nits^ho</i>	<i>nits^ho</i>
109.	older sister	दिदी	<i>nana</i>	<i>nana</i>	<i>nana</i>	<i>nana</i>	<i>nana</i>
110.	younger sister	बहिनी	<i>baĩni</i>	<i>baĩni</i>	<i>baĩni</i>	<i>baĩni</i>	<i>baĩni</i>

111	son	छोरो	<i>toroppa</i>	<i>toroppa</i>	<i>toroppa</i>	<i>toroppa</i>	<i>toroppa</i>
112	daughter	छोरी	<i>tsjo</i>	<i>tsjo</i>	<i>tsjo</i>	<i>tsjo</i>	<i>tsjo</i>
113	husband	लोप्रे (श्रीमान)	<i>kimi</i>	<i>kimi</i>	<i>kimi</i>	<i>kimi</i>	<i>kimi</i>
114	wife	स्वाम्नी (श्रीमती)	<i>mɔi</i>	<i>mɔi</i>	<i>mɔi</i>	<i>mɔi</i>	<i>mɔi</i>
115	boy	केटो	<i>sorts^ha</i>	<i>sorts^ha</i>	<i>sorts^ha</i>	<i>sorts^ha</i>	<i>sorts^ha</i>
116	girl	केटी	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>	<i>mari</i>
117	day	दिन	<i>k^holɔi</i>	<i>k^holɔi</i>	<i>k^holɔi</i>	<i>k^holɔi</i>	<i>k^holɔi</i>
118	night	रात	<i>k^hosɔi</i>	<i>k^hosɔi</i>	<i>k^hosɔi</i>	<i>k^hosɔi</i>	<i>k^hosɔi</i>
119	morning	विहान	<i>wapo</i>	<i>wapo</i>	<i>wapo</i>	<i>wapo</i>	<i>wapo</i>
120	noon	मध्यान्ह	<i>k^holɔima</i>	<i>k^holɔima</i>	<i>k^holɔima</i>	<i>k^holɔima</i>	<i>k^holɔima</i>
121	evening	साँझ	<i>namnuɣma</i>	<i>namnuɣma</i>	<i>namnuɣma</i>	<i>namnuɣma</i>	<i>namnuɣma</i>
122	yesterday	हिजो	<i>ase</i>	<i>ase</i>	<i>ase</i>	<i>ase</i>	<i>ase</i>
123	today	आज	<i>ale</i>	<i>ale</i>	<i>ale</i>	<i>ale</i>	<i>ale</i>
124	tomorrow	भोली	<i>selama</i>	<i>selama</i>	<i>selama</i>	<i>selama</i>	<i>selama</i>
125	week	हप्ता (साता)	<i>ɸapta</i>	<i>ɸapta</i>	<i>ɸapta</i>	<i>ɸapta</i>	<i>ɸapta</i>
126	month	महिना	<i>mamsuɣ</i>	<i>mamsuɣ</i>	<i>mamsuɣ</i>	<i>mamsuɣ</i>	<i>mamsuɣ</i>
127	year	वर्ष	<i>duɣ</i>	<i>duɣ</i>	<i>duɣ</i>	<i>duɣ</i>	<i>duɣ</i>
128	old	बूढो	<i>ɔiɰako</i>	<i>ɔiɰako</i>	<i>ɔiɰako</i>	<i>ɔiɰako</i>	<i>ɔiɰako</i>
129	new	नयाँ	<i>alseko</i>	<i>alseko</i>	<i>alseko</i>	<i>alseko</i>	<i>alseko</i>
130	good	राम्रो (असल)	<i>k^huinjo</i>	<i>k^huinjo</i>	<i>k^huinjo</i>	<i>k^huinjo</i>	<i>k^huinjo</i>
131	bad	नराम्रो (खराब)	<i>k^hɔisa</i>	<i>k^hɔisa</i>	<i>k^hɔisa</i>	<i>k^hɔisa</i>	<i>k^hɔisa</i>
132	wet	चिसो	<i>ɸopako</i>	<i>ɸopako</i>	<i>ɸopako</i>	<i>ɸopako</i>	<i>ɸopako</i>
133	dry	सुख्खा	<i>ɸasako</i>	<i>ɸasako</i>	<i>ɸasako</i>	<i>ɸasako</i>	<i>ɸasako</i>
134	long	लामो	<i>mɔid^hako</i>	<i>mɔid^hako</i>	<i>mɔid^hako</i>	<i>mɔid^hako</i>	<i>mɔid^hako</i>
135	short	छोटो	<i>tsud^hako</i>	<i>tsud^hako</i>	<i>tsud^hako</i>	<i>tsud^hako</i>	<i>tsud^hako</i>
136	hot	तातो	<i>pɸhudeko</i>	<i>pɸhudeko</i>	<i>pɸhudeko</i>	<i>pɸhudeko</i>	<i>pɸhudeko</i>
137	cold	चिसो	<i>remako</i>	<i>remako</i>	<i>remako</i>	<i>remako</i>	<i>remako</i>
138	right	दाहिने	<i>ɸjakka</i>	<i>ɸjakka</i>	<i>ɸjakka</i>	<i>ɸjakka</i>	<i>ɸjakka</i>
139	left	देब्रे	<i>uɸjakka</i>	<i>uɸjakka</i>	<i>uɸjakka</i>	<i>uɸjakka</i>	<i>uɸjakka</i>
140	near	नजिक	<i>oɰako</i>	<i>oɰako</i>	<i>oɰako</i>	<i>oɰako</i>	<i>oɰako</i>
141	far	टाढा	<i>ɸjalo</i>	<i>ɸjalo</i>	<i>ɸjalo</i>	<i>ɸjalo</i>	<i>ɸjalo</i>
142	big	ठूलो	<i>mɔiɰa</i>	<i>mɔiɰa</i>	<i>mɔiɰa</i>	<i>mɔiɰa</i>	<i>mɔiɰa</i>
143	small	सानो	<i>ikiniko</i>	<i>ikiniko</i>	<i>ikiniko</i>	<i>ikiniko</i>	<i>ikiniko</i>
144	heavy	गह्रौँ	<i>d^hiseko</i>	<i>d^hiseko</i>	<i>d^hiseko</i>	<i>d^hiseko</i>	<i>d^hiseko</i>
145	light	हलुका	<i>ihōsa</i>	<i>ihōsa</i>	<i>ihōsa</i>	<i>ihōsa</i>	<i>ihōsa</i>
146	above	माथि	<i>ɰ^halo</i>	<i>ɰ^halo</i>	<i>ɰ^halo</i>	<i>ɰ^halo</i>	<i>ɰ^halo</i>

147	below	तल	<i>fuilo</i>	<i>fuilo</i>	<i>fuilo</i>	<i>fuilo</i>	<i>fuilo</i>
148	white	सेतो	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>	<i>opatsima</i>
149	black	कालो	<i>maktsupa</i>	<i>maktsupa</i>	<i>maktsupa</i>	<i>maktsupa</i>	<i>maktsupa</i>
150	red	रातो	<i>hipatipa</i>	<i>hipatipa</i>	<i>hipatipa</i>	<i>hipatipa</i>	<i>hipatipa</i>
151	one	एक	<i>iʔo</i>	<i>iʔo</i>	<i>iʔo</i>	<i>iʔo</i>	<i>iʔo</i>
152	two	दुई	<i>hʃaka</i>	<i>hʃaka</i>	<i>hʃaka</i>	<i>hʃaka</i>	<i>hʃaka</i>
153	three	तीन	<i>simra</i>	<i>simra</i>	<i>simra</i>	<i>simra</i>	<i>simra</i>
154	four	चार	<i>ljura</i>	<i>ljura</i>	<i>ljura</i>	<i>ljura</i>	<i>ljura</i>
155	five	पाँच	<i>ɳara</i>	<i>ɳara</i>	<i>ɳara</i>	<i>ɳara</i>	<i>ɳara</i>
156	six	छ	<i>ɳa</i>	<i>ɳa</i>	<i>ɳa</i>	<i>ɳa</i>	<i>ɳa</i>
157	seven	सात	<i>suka</i>	<i>suka</i>	<i>suka</i>	<i>suka</i>	<i>suka</i>
158	eight	आठ	<i>nuka</i>	<i>nuka</i>	<i>nuka</i>	<i>nuka</i>	<i>nuka</i>
159	nine	नौ	<i>nunam</i>	<i>nunam</i>	<i>nunam</i>	<i>nunam</i>	<i>nunam</i>
160	ten	दश	<i>iknam</i>	<i>iknam</i>	<i>iknam</i>	<i>iknam</i>	<i>iknam</i>
161	eleven	एघार	<i>ikik</i>	<i>ikik</i>	<i>ikik</i>	<i>ikik</i>	<i>ikik</i>
162	twelve	बाह्र	<i>ikhaka</i>	<i>ikhaka</i>	<i>ikhaka</i>	<i>ikhaka</i>	<i>ikhaka</i>
163	twenty	बीस	<i>hanam</i>	<i>hanam</i>	<i>hanam</i>	<i>hanam</i>	<i>hanam</i>
164	one hundred	एक सय	<i>namranam</i>	<i>namrana m</i>	<i>namranam</i>	<i>namranam</i>	<i>namranam</i>
165	who	को	<i>so</i>	<i>so</i>	<i>so</i>	<i>so</i>	<i>so</i>
166	what	के	<i>de</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>de</i>
167	where	कहाँ	<i>kʰoɖa</i>	<i>kʰoɖa</i>	<i>kʰoɖa</i>	<i>kʰoɖa</i>	<i>kʰoɖa</i>
168	when	कहिले	<i>delo</i>	<i>delo</i>	<i>delo</i>	<i>delo</i>	<i>delo</i>
169	how many	कति	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>
170	which	कुन	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>	<i>demno</i>
171	this	यो	<i>oko</i>	<i>oko</i>	<i>oko</i>	<i>oko</i>	<i>oko</i>
172	that	त्यो	<i>tiko</i>	<i>tiko</i>	<i>tiko</i>	<i>tiko</i>	<i>tiko</i>
173	these	यिनीहरू	<i>okotsi</i>	<i>okotsi</i>	<i>okotsi</i>	<i>okotsi</i>	<i>okotsi</i>
174	those	उनीहरू	<i>kʰutsi</i>	<i>kʰutsi</i>	<i>kʰutsi</i>	<i>kʰutsi</i>	<i>kʰutsi</i>
175	same	उही	<i>tsiko</i>	<i>tsiko</i>	<i>tsiko</i>	<i>tsiko</i>	<i>tsiko</i>
176	different	फरक (अलग)	<i>kʰalkʰal</i>	<i>kʰalkʰal</i>	<i>kʰalkʰal</i>	<i>kʰalkʰal</i>	<i>kʰalkʰal</i>
177	whole	सबै	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>
178	broken	फुटेको	<i>kʰleʔako</i>	<i>kʰleʔako</i>	<i>kʰleʔako</i>	<i>kʰleʔako</i>	<i>kʰleʔako</i>
179	few	थोरै	<i>pitsʰa</i>	<i>pitsʰa</i>	<i>pitsʰa</i>	<i>pitsʰa</i>	<i>pitsʰa</i>
180	many	धेरै	<i>kebʰa</i>	<i>kebʰa</i>	<i>kebʰa</i>	<i>kebʰa</i>	<i>kebʰa</i>
181	all	सबै	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>	<i>dzʰara</i>
182	to eat	खानु	<i>tsama</i>	<i>tsama</i>	<i>tsama</i>	<i>tsama</i>	<i>tsama</i>
183	to bite	टोकु	<i>kʰramma</i>	<i>kʰramma</i>	<i>kʰramma</i>	<i>kʰramma</i>	<i>kʰramma</i>
184	to be hungry	भोकाउनु	<i>sakama</i>	<i>sakama</i>	<i>sakama</i>	<i>sakama</i>	<i>sakama</i>
185	to drink	पिउनु	<i>duɳma</i>	<i>duɳma</i>	<i>duɳma</i>	<i>duɳma</i>	<i>duɳma</i>
186	to be	तिर्खाउनु	<i>waima</i>	<i>waima</i>	<i>waima</i>	<i>waima</i>	<i>waima</i>

	thirsty						
187	to sleep	सुत्नु	<i>imma</i>	<i>imma</i>	<i>imma</i>	<i>imma</i>	<i>imma</i>
188	to lie	पल्टनु	<i>limma</i>	<i>limma</i>	<i>limma</i>	<i>limma</i>	<i>limma</i>
189	to sit	बसुनु	<i>juɣma</i>	<i>juɣma</i>	<i>juɣma</i>	<i>juɣma</i>	<i>juɣma</i>
190	to give	दिनु	<i>ima</i>	<i>ima</i>	<i>ima</i>	<i>ima</i>	<i>ima</i>
191	to burn	डढाउनु	<i>ɦuima</i>	<i>ɦuima</i>	<i>ɦuima</i>	<i>ɦuima</i>	<i>ɦuima</i>
192	to die	मर्नु	<i>sima</i>	<i>sima</i>	<i>sima</i>	<i>sima</i>	<i>sima</i>
193	to kill	मार्नु	<i>sɔima</i>	<i>sɔima</i>	<i>sɔima</i>	<i>sɔima</i>	<i>sɔima</i>
194	to fly	उडनु	<i>perma</i>	<i>perma</i>	<i>perma</i>	<i>perma</i>	<i>perma</i>
195	to walk	हिँडनु	<i>lamt^hima</i>	<i>lamt^hima</i>	<i>lamt^hima</i>	<i>lamt^hima</i>	<i>lamt^hima</i>
196	to run/ run	दौडनु	<i>ɲuima</i>	<i>ɲuima</i>	<i>ɲuima</i>	<i>ɲuima</i>	<i>ɲuima</i>
197	to go /go	जानु	<i>k^hɔima</i>	<i>k^hɔima</i>	<i>k^hɔima</i>	<i>k^hɔima</i>	<i>k^hɔima</i>
198	to come	आउनु	<i>buima</i>	<i>buima</i>	<i>buima</i>	<i>buima</i>	<i>buima</i>
199	to speak/ speak	बोल्नु	<i>plima</i>	<i>plima</i>	<i>plima</i>	<i>plima</i>	<i>plima</i>
200	to hear/hear/li sten	सुत्नु	<i>ɔima</i>	<i>ɔima</i>	<i>ɔima</i>	<i>ɔima</i>	<i>ɔima</i>
201	to look/look	हेर्नु	<i>k^homa</i>	<i>k^homa</i>	<i>k^homa</i>	<i>k^homa</i>	<i>k^homa</i>
202	I	म	<i>kā</i>	<i>kā</i>	<i>kā</i>	<i>kā</i>	<i>kā</i>
203	you (informal)	तँ	<i>k^hana</i>	<i>k^hana</i>	<i>k^hana</i>	<i>k^hana</i>	<i>k^hana</i>
204	you (formal)	तपाईं	<i>k^hɔini</i>	<i>k^hɔini</i>	<i>k^hɔini</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>
205	he	ऊ	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>
206	she	उनी	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>	<i>k^hu</i>
207	we (inclusive)	हामी (समावेशी)	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^htsi</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>
208	we (exclusive)	हामी (असमावे शी)	<i>katska</i>	<i>katska</i>	<i>katska</i>	<i>katska</i>	<i>katska</i>
209	you (plural)	तिमीहरू	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^heni</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>	<i>k^hɔitsi</i>
210	they	उनीहरू	<i>k^hutsi</i>	<i>k^hutsi</i>	<i>k^hutsa</i>	<i>k^hutsi</i>	<i>k^hutsi</i>

Annex B: Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A

Shaded items are NOT to be read aloud.

Introduce yourself first:

My name is I am from Central Department of Linguistics, Tribhuvan University. I am a research assistant of the Linguistic Survey of Nepal. I am here to learn about your language and its situation. We will share the information given by you with others. Are you willing to help us?

INFORMED CONSENT: Given: Not Given:

A. Meta data (Baseline information)

Enter the answers to the following BEFORE the INTERVIEW:

Question	Answer
Interview Number	
Date	Day..... Month.....Year..... VS Day.....Month Year..... AD
Place of Interview	Ward No: Village/Town: VDC/Municipality: District: Zone: GPS Coordinates:EN
Interviewer Name	(a) (b) (c) (d)

	(e)
Language of Elicitation	
Language of Response	
Interpreter Name (if needed)	

8. Name of language consultant:

9. (Ask if needed) Sex: (a) Male (b) Female (c) Other

10. Age group: (i) 15-34 (ii) 35-60 (iii) 60+

11. Are you literate?

(a) Yes (b) No

12. (If "Yes") How did you learn to read & write?

(a) Formally (b) Non-formally

13. (If "Formally") What year/level did you complete?

(a) Primary (b) Lower Secondary (c) Secondary

(d) Higher (specify highest degree).....

14. Marital status: (a) Married (b) Unmarried

15. (If "Married") Do you have any children?

(a) Yes (b) No

16. Caste

17. Ethnic group:

18. Religion:

(a) Hinduism (b) Buddhism (c) Kirant (d) Christianity (e) Jain

(f) Islam (g) Shamanism (h) Other

19. Your mother tongue's name:

(a) (Given by respondent).....

20. Name given by the nonnative speakers for your language (tapaiko bhasha nabholne manchele tapaiko bhasalai ke bhanchan?).....

21. Different names of the language if any (yo bhashalai aru naamle pani chinincha?)

(i)..... (ii)

(iii)..... (iv)

22. Your mother's mother tongue.....

23. Your father's mother tongue.....

SCREENING CRITERIA #1: At least one parent from target MT. YES NO

24. Mother tongue of your husband/ wife

25. What village were you born in?

(a) Ward No..... (b) Village/Town..... (c) VDC/municipality..... (d)

District..... (d) Zone.....

Where do you live now?

How many years have you lived here?
 Have you lived anywhere else for more than a year?
 (if so) Where? When? How long did you live there?

SCREENING CRITERIA #2:	YES <input type="checkbox"/>
NO <input type="checkbox"/>	
Grew up here, Live here now, and, If they have lived elsewhere, it is not a significant amount of recent time.	

B. Language resources

30. What are the major kinds of Oral literature available in your language?

- (a) folk tales,
- (b) songs,
- (c) religious literature,
- (d) radio,
- (e) films,
- (f) CD/ DVD,
- (g) Other.....

31. (If they mentioned radio programs) How often do you listen to radio program broadcast in your language?

- (a) Usually (b) Sometimes (c) Never

32. (only ask literate language consultants) What materials written about your language?

33. (If “Yes”) What language(s) is it written in?

Material:	32. Yes or No	33. (If “Yes”) What language(s) is it written in?
a. Phonemic inventory		
b. Grammar		
c. Dictionary		
d. Textbooks		
Literacy materials		
Newspapers		
Magazines		
Written literature		
Folklore		
Other		

34. (If they mentioned written materials) Do you read any of these things written in your language?

- (a) Yes (b) No

35. (Only ask literate consultants, if their language has written materials):

What script(s) is your language written in?

36. Are there any organizations that promote the knowledge and/ or use of the language?

- (a) Yes (b) No

37. (If “Yes”) Please name those organizations. (enter below)

38. What kinds of activities do each organization perform? (enter below)

- (a) Cultural
- (b) Linguistic
- (c) Educational
- (d) Other.....

	36. Organization	37. Kinds of activities
i.		
ii.		
iii.		
iv.		
v.		
vi.		

C. Mother-tongue Proficiency and Multilingualism

39. What languages can you speak?

40. What language did you speak first?

So you speak... (remind of Q. 38)

Which language do you speak...

41. best?

42. second best?

43. third best?

44. fourth best?

45. Among the languages that you speak which one do you love the most?

46. (Only ask if MT was not best language) Please estimate how proficient are you in your mother tongue:

- (a) Very Well
- (b) Some
- (c) Only a Little

47. Please estimate how well you can read and write your mother tongue:

- (a) Very Well
- (b) Some
- (c) Only a Little

48. Other languages known to your father (enter below)

49. Other Languages known to your mother (enter below)

50. Other Languages known to your spouse (enter below)

Persons	Other Languages			
	a	b	C	d
48. Father				
49. Mother				
50. Spouse				

51. What languages are spoken by your sons/ daughters? (enter below)

52. Where did they learn those languages? (enter below)

	50. Other languages spoken by children:	51. Where learned:
a.		
b.		
c.		
d.		
e.		
f.		

53. When a small child first goes to school, can (s)he understand everything his/her Nepali speaking teacher says?

(a) Yes (d) A little bit (c) No

D. Domain of Language Use

54. Which language do you use most frequently for the following purposes?

	Domain	Language
A	Counting	
B	Singing	
C	Joking	
D	Bargaining/ Shopping/ Marketing	
E	Story telling	
F	Discussing/ Debate	
G	Praying	
H	Quarrelling	
I	Abusing (scolding/using taboo words)	
J	Telling stories to children	
K	Singing at home	
L	Family gatherings	
M	Village meetings	

55. Languages most frequently used at home in the following situations:
 (a) talking about education matters (like school, admission, studies, teacher, etc.)
 (enter below)

(b) Discussing social events and family matters (like festivals, election, ceremonies, marriage, savings, spending, etc.) (enter below)

(c) While writing letters? (enter below)

	a. Education Matters	b. Social Events & Family Matters	c. Writing Letters
i. Grandfather:			
ii. Grandmother:			
iii. Father:			
iv. Mother:			
v. Spouse:			
vi. Children:			

56. What language do your children usually speak while:

(a) playing with other children?

(b) talking with neighbors?

(c) at school?

57. What language does your community use for marriage invitations?

58. What language is usually used to write minutes in community meetings?

59. How often do you use your mother tongue?

(a) Every day (b) Rarely (c) Never

60. How often do you use the language of wider communication (LWC)?

(a) Every day (b) Rarely (c) Never

61. Which language do you usually use when speakers of other languages visit you at home?

62. What language do you prefer for your children's medium of instruction at primary level?

(a) Mother tongue (b) Nepali (c) English (d) Other.....

E. Language Vitality

63. Do all your children speak your mother tongue?

(a) Yes (b) No

64. What language do most parents in this village usually speak with their children?

(a) Mother tongue (b) Nepali (c) Other.....

65. Do young people in your village/town speak your mother tongue well, the way it ought to be spoken?

(a) Yes (b) No

F. Language Maintenance

66. Is there intermarriage in your community?

- (a) Yes (b) No
67. (If “Yes”) Which other language groups have common marital relationship with your language group?
 (i)..... (ii)..... (iii).....
68. Do you like your children learn/study in mother tongue?
 (a) Yes (b) No
69. (If “Yes”) If schools are opened for teaching your language will you support it:
 (a) by sending your children?
 (b) by encouraging other people to send their children?
 (c) by providing financial help?
 (d) by teaching?
 (e) by helping with the school?
 (f) other.....

G. Language Attitudes

70. When you speak your mother tongue in the presence of the speaker of the dominant language what do you feel...
 (a) Prestigious (b) Embarrassed (c) Neutral
71. Have you ever had any problem because of being a native speaker of your mother tongue?
 (a) Yes (b) No
72. (If “Yes”) What kinds of problems have you had?(These options are not to be listed in the SLQ, but left as categories in the database.)
 (a) Social discrimination.
 (b) Political discrimination.
 (c) Economic discrimination.
 (d) Hostile confrontation.
 (e) Discrimination in education.
 (f) Social pressure.
 (g) Political pressure.
 (h) Economic pressure.
 (i) Other
73. How would you feel if your son or daughter married someone who does not know your language?
 (a) Good (b) Indifferent(c) Bad
74. When the children of your village grow up and have children do you think those children might speak your language?
 (a) Yes (b) No
75. How do you feel about this?
 (a) Good (b) Indifferent(c) Bad
76. What language should your children speak first?
77. Do you think that the language spoken by you is different from your grandparents?
 (a) Yes (b) No
78. (If “Yes”) How?
 (a) pronunciation
 (b) vocabulary
 (c) use of specific type of sentences
 (d) mixing of other languages
 (e) way of speaking

(f) Other.....

79. How do you feel when you hear young people of your own community speaking other languages instead of their first language?

(a) Good (b) Indifferent (c) Bad

Comments (anything unusual or noteworthy about this interview)

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A (in Nepali)

छायाकृत कुराहरू मनमनै पढने।

सर्वप्रथम आफ्नो परिचय दिने: मेरो/हाम्रो नाम हो। (अरूले पनि आ-आफ्नो परिचय दिने)। हामी त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय भाषाविज्ञान केन्द्रीय विभागबाट यहाँहरूको भाषाको अध्ययन अनुसन्धानका लागि आएका हौं। यहाँहरूले दिनु भएको भाषासम्बन्धी जानकारीलाई अरूसँग राख्ने छौं। यसमा यहाँहरूले आफ्नो सहमतिका साथ सहयोग गर्नु हुने छ भने आशा राखेका छौं।

सहमति: छ छैन

(अ) आधारभूत सूचना

अन्तर्वार्ता भन्दा पहिले तलका प्रश्नहरू (१-७) को उत्तर लेख्नु होस्।

प्रश्न	उत्तर
१. अन्तर्वार्ता संख्या	
२. मिति	गते..... महिना..... वर्ष..... वि.सं. तारिख..... महिना वर्ष..... सन्
३. अन्तर्वार्ता स्थान	वार्ड नं.: गाउँ/नगर: गाविस/नगरपालिका: जिल्ला: अञ्चल: जिपिएस कोओर्डिनेट्स:..... पू. उ.

४. अनुसन्धाता(हरू)को नाम:	(क) (ख) (ग) (घ) (ङ)
५. अन्तर्वार्ताको माध्यम भाषा
६. अन्तर्क्रियाको माध्यम भाषा
७. दोभाषेको नाम (आवश्यक परेमा)

८. भाषासूचकको नाम:

९. (आवश्यक परेमा मात्र) लिङ्ग: (क) पुरुष (ख) महिला (ग) अन्य

१०. उमेर:

११. तपाईंलाई लेख-पढ गर्न आउँछ?

(क) आउँछ (ख) आउँदैन

१२. (आउँछ भने) तपाईंले लेख-पढ गर्न कसरी सिकु भयो?

(क) औपचारिक रूपमा (ख) अनौपचारिक रूपमा

१३. (औपचारिक रूपमा हो भने) कुन तह उत्तीर्ण गर्नु भएको छ?

(क) प्राथमिक (ख) निम्न माध्यमिक (ग) माध्यमिक

(घ) उच्च (उच्चतम तह उल्लेख गर्ने)

१४. वैवाहिक अवस्था: (क) विवाहित (ख) अविवाहित

१५. (विवाहित भएमा) तपाईंका छोराछोरी छन् कि छैनन्?

(क) छन् (ख) छैनन्

१६. जाति:.....

१७. जनजाति समूह (थर):

१८. धर्म:

(क) हिन्दू (ख) बौद्ध (ग) किरात (घ) इसाई (ङ) जैन

(च) इस्लाम (छ) प्रकृतिपूजक (ज) अन्य.....

१९. तपाईंको मातृभाषाको नाम:

(क) (तपाईंले भन्ने).....

२०. तपाईंको भन्दा अन्य भाषा समुदायका (तपाईंको भाषा नबोल्ने) मान्छेले तपाईंको भाषालाई के भन्छन्?.....

२१. यो भाषालाई अरु नामले पनि चिनिन्छ? (यस भाषाका अरु के के नाम छन्?)

(क) (ख)

(ग) (घ)

२२. तपाईंकी आमाको मातृभाषा:

२३. तपाईंको बुबाको मातृभाषा:

छनौटको आधार #१ कम्तीमा बाबु अथवा आमा मध्ये एक मातृभाषी हुनुपर्ने।

छ छैन

२४. तपाईंको श्रीमान्/श्रीमतीको मातृभाषा:

२५. तपाईं जन्मेको स्थान/गाउँ कहाँ हो?

(क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:

(ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:

(ङ) अञ्चल:

२६. हाल तपाईं कहाँ बस्नु हुन्छ?

(क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:

(ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:

(ङ) अञ्चल:

२७. तपाईं यहाँ बस्नु भएको कति समय भयो?.....

२८. तपाईं अन्त कतै एक वर्ष भन्दा बढी बस्नु भएको छ?

(क) छ (ख) छैन

२९. (यदि बस्नु भएको छ भने)

(क) कहाँ: (ख) कहिले: (ग) कति समयसम्म:

छनौटको आधार #२ यहाँ हुर्केको, अहिले यहाँ बसेको, र यदि पाँच वर्ष भन्दा बढी अन्यत्र बसेको भए यहाँ पनि गत पाँच वर्ष देखि नै बसेको हुनु पर्ने।

हो होइन

(आ) भाषिक सामग्री

३०. तपाईंको भाषामा मौखिक साहित्य के-के उपलब्ध छन्?

(क) लोक कथा,

(ख) संगीत,

(ग) धार्मिक साहित्य,

(घ) रेडियो,

(ङ) सिनेमा,

(च) सीडी/डीभीडी,

(छ) अन्य:.....

३१. (रेडियो कार्यक्रम छ भने) तपाईं आफ्नो मातृभाषामा रेडियो कार्यक्रम कतिको सुन्नु हुन्छ?

(क) सधैं (ख) कहिले काहीँ (ग) कहिले पनि होइन

३२. (साक्षर भाषासूचकलाई मात्र सोध्ने) तपाईंको भाषाको बारेमा लिखित सामग्री के-के छन्?

३३. (छन् भने) कुन भाषामा लेखिएका छन्?

सामग्री:	३२. छन् वा छैनन्	३३. (छन् भने) कुन भाषामा लेखिएका छन्?
क. वर्णमाला		
ख. व्याकरण		

ग. शब्दकोष		
घ. पाठ्यपुस्तक		
साक्षरता सामग्री		
समाचारपत्र		
छ. पत्रिका		
ज. लिखित साहित्य		
झ. लोकवार्ता		
अन्य		

३४. (लिखित सामग्रीहरू छन् भने) तपाईं आफ्नो भाषामा माथिका सामग्री मध्ये कुनै पढ्नु हुन्छ?

(क) पढ्छु (ख) पढदिन

३५. (साक्षर सूचकलाई मात्र सोध्ने, उनीहरूको भाषामा लिखित सामग्री छन् भने):

तपाईंको भाषा कुन लिपिमा लेखिन्छ?

३६. तपाईंको भाषामा भएको ज्ञान अथवा उपयोगलाई विकास वा प्रवर्द्धनमा लागिपरेका कुनै संघसंस्था वा निकायहरू छन्?

(क) छन् (ख) छैनन्

३७. (छन् भने) ती संस्थाहरूको नाम भनी दिनु होस्।

३८. ती संस्थाले के कस्ता काम गर्छन्?

(क) सांस्कृतिक

(ख) भाषिक

(ग) शैक्षिक

(घ) अन्य.....

	३७. संघसंस्था	३८. क्रियाकलाप
क.		
ख.		
ग.		
घ.		
ङ.		
च.		

(इ) मातृभाषामा दक्षता/बहुभाषिकता

३९. तपाईं कुन कुन भाषा बोल्न सक्नु हुन्छ?

-,,,
४०. तपाईंले सबै भन्दा पहिले कुन भाषा बोल्नु भयो?
- यी भाषाहरूमध्ये (प्रश्न नं. ३९ को उत्तरको आधारमा) कुन भाषा:
४१. सबै भन्दा राम्रो?
४२. दोस्रो राम्रो?
४३. तेस्रो राम्रो?
४४. चौथो राम्रो?
४५. तपाईंले बोल्ने भाषाहरू मध्ये कुन चाहीं सबै भन्दा बढी मन पराउनु हुन्छ?.....
४६. (मातृभाषा सबैभन्दा राम्ररी बोल्न नसकेमा) तपाईं आफ्नो मातृभाषामा कत्तिको पोख्त(दक्ष) हुनु हुन्छ?
- (क) धेरै राम्रो (ख) ठिक ठिकै (ग) अलि अलि
४७. तपाईं आफ्नो मातृभाषा कत्तिको राम्रो पढ्न र लेख्न सक्नु हुन्छ?
- (क) धेरै राम्रो (ख) ठिक ठिकै (ग) अलि अलि
४८. तपाईंको बुवाले अन्य कुन कुन भाषा जान्नु हुन्छ? (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)
४९. तपाईंको आमाको अन्य कुन कुन भाषा जान्नु हुन्छ? (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)
५०. तपाईंको श्रीमान्/श्रीमतीले अन्य कुन कुन भाषा जान्नु हुन्छ? (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

व्यक्ति	अन्य भाषाहरू			
	क.	ख.	ग.	घ.
४८. बुवा				
४९. आमा				
५०. श्रीमान्/श्रीमती				

५१. तपाईंका छोराछोरीहरूले कुन कुन भाषा बोल्छन्? (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)
५२. तिनीहरूले ती भाषाहरू कहाँ सिके? (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

	५१. छोराछोरीले बोल्ने अन्य भाषा	५२. कहाँ सिकेको?
क.		
ख.		
ग.		
घ.		
ङ.		
च.		

५३. भर्खर स्कूल जान थालेका स-साना नानीले शिक्षक-शिक्षिकाले कक्षामा नेपालीमा भनेका सबै कुरा बुझ्छन्?
- (क) सबै बुझ्छन् (ख) अलि अलि बुझ्छन् (ग) बुझ्दैनन्
- (ई) भाषाको प्रयोग

५४. तल उल्लेख गरिएका काम गर्दा तपाईं सबै भन्दा बढी कुन भाषा प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?

	काम	भाषा
क.	गन्ती गर्दा	
ख.	गीत गाउँदा	
ग.	ठट्टा गर्दा	
घ.	हाटबजार गर्दा/मोलतोल गर्दा	
ङ.	कथा भन्दा	
च.	छलफल/वादविवाद गर्दा	
छ.	प्रार्थना गर्दा	
ज.	झगडा गर्दा	
झ.	गाली गर्दा	
ञ.	केटाकेटीलाई कथा सुनाउँदा	
ट.	घरमा गीत गाउँदा	
ठ.	पारिवारिक जमघटमा	
ड.	गाँउको बैठकमा	

५५. तपाईंको घरमा निम्नलिखित विषयमा कुराकानी हुँदा सबै भन्दा बढी बोलिने भाषा कुन हो?

(क) शिक्षा सम्बन्धी कुराकानी गर्दा (जस्तै: विद्यालय, भर्ना, पढाइ, शिक्षकशिक्षिका सम्बन्धी) (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

(ख) सामाजिक क्रियाकलाप र पारिवारिक विषयमा छलफल गर्दा (जस्तै: चाडपर्व, चुनाव, उत्सव, विवाह, वचत, खर्च सम्बन्धी) (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

(ग) चिठीपत्र लेख्दा (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

	क. शिक्षा सम्बन्धी	ख. सामाजिक क्रियाकलाप र पारिवारिक विषयमा	ग. चिठीपत्र लेख्दा
क. हजुरबुबासँग			
ख. हजुरआमासँग			
ग. बुबासँग			
घ. आमासँग			
ङ. श्रीमान्/श्रीमतीसँग			

५६. तपाईंका बालबालिका निम्नलिखित अवस्थामा प्राय जसो कुन भाषा प्रयोग गर्छन्?
 (क) अन्य साथीहरूसँग खेल्दा
 (ख) छिमेकीहरूसँग कुराकानी गर्दा
 (ग) विद्यालयमा
५७. विहेको निम्तो गर्नु पर्दा तपाईंहरू कुन भाषाको प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?
५८. समुदायका बैठकमा भएका निर्णय लेख्नु पर्दा कुन भाषाको प्रयोग गरिन्छ?
५९. तपाईं आफ्नो मातृभाषा कतिको प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?
 (क) दिन दिनै (ख) कहिले काहीं (ग) कहिल्यै गर्दिन
६०. तपाईंको सम्पर्क भाषा कुन हो र त्यसको कति प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?
 भाषाको नाम:
 (क) दिन दिनै (ख) कहिले काहीं (ग) कहिल्यै गर्दिन
६१. तपाईंको भन्दा बेग्लै भाषा बोल्ने साथीभाइ तपाईंका घरमा आउँदा कुन भाषाको प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?

६२. तपाईंका छोराछोरीलाई प्राथमिक तहमा कुन भाषाको माध्यममा पढाउन चाहनु हुन्छ?
 (क) मातृभाषा(ख) नेपाली (ग) अंग्रेजी (घ) अन्य.....
 (उ) भाषिक जीवन्तता
६३. तपाईंका सबै छोराछोरीले मातृभाषा बोल्छन्?
 (क) बोल्छन् (ख) बोल्दैनन्
६४. यस गाउँका धेरै जसो अभिभावकहरू आफ्ना केटाकेटीसँग कुराकानी गर्दा प्रायः कुन भाषाको प्रयोग गर्छन्?
 (क) मातृभाषा(ख) नेपाली (ग) अन्य.....
६५. तपाईंका समुदायका युवायुवतीले यो भाषा जति राम्रो बोल्नु पर्ने हो त्यति नै राम्ररी बोल्छन्?
 (क) बोल्छन् (ख) बोल्दैनन्
 (उ) भाषिक निरन्तरता
६६. तपाईंको समुदायमा अन्तर्जातीय विवाह हुन्छ?
 (क) हुन्छ (ख) हुँदैन
६७. (हुन्छ भने) अन्य कुन भाषिक समुदायसँग तपाईंहरूको परस्पर वैवाहिक सम्बन्ध छ?
 (क)..... (ख) (ग)
६८. आफ्ना केटाकेटीले मातृभाषामा पढ्ने लेख्ने गरेको तपाईं मन पराउनु हुन्छ?
 (क) पराउँछु (ख) पराउँदिन
६९. (पराउँनु हुन्छ भने) तपाईंको भाषा पढाउने स्कूल खोलियो भने कसरी सहयोग गर्नु हुन्छ?

- (क) आफ्ना केटाकेटीलाई पढ्न पठाएर
 (ख) समुदायका अरूलाई आफ्ना केटाकेटीहरू पठाउन प्रोत्साहित गरेर
 (ग) आर्थिक सहयोग प्रदान गरेर
 (घ) आफैले अध्यापन गरेर
 (ङ) स्कूललाई सहयोग गरेर

(च) अन्य प्रकारले

(ए) भाषिक अभिवृत्ति

७०. प्रभावकारी (dominant) भाषा बोल्ने व्यक्तिहरूको बीचमा तपाईंलाई आफ्नो मातृभाषा बोल्दा कस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) प्रतिष्ठा बढे जस्तो लाग्छ (ख) अप्ठ्यारो लाग्छ (ग) त्यस्तो केही लाग्दैन

७१. मातृभाषी भएकै कारण तपाईंले कहिल्यै कुनै समस्या भोग्नु भएको छ?

(क) छ (ख) छैन

७२. (छ भन्ने) के कस्तो समस्या भोग्नु भएको छ?

७३. तपाईंका छोरा वा छोरीले तपाईंको मातृभाषा बोल्न नजान्ने मान्छेसित विवाह गरे भने तपाईंलाई कस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) राम्रो (ख) ठिकै (ग) नराम्रो

७४. अहिलेका केटाकेटीका छोराछोरीले पनि तपाईंको भाषा बोल्लान्?

(क) बोल्लान् (ख) नबोल्लान्

७५. बोले भने तपाईंलाई कस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) राम्रो (ख) ठिकै (ग) खराब

७६. बोलेनन् भने कस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) राम्रो (ख) ठिकै (ग) खराब

७७. तपाईंका छोराछोरीले सबैभन्दा पहिले कुन भाषा बोल्नु पर्छ?

७८. तपाईंले बोल्ने भाषा तपाईंका हजुरबुबा/हजुरआमाले बोल्ने भाषा भन्दा फरक भए जस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) लाग्छ (ख) लाग्दैन

७९. (लाग्छ भने) के केमा फरक होला?

(क) उच्चारणमा

(ख) शब्दभण्डारमा

(ग) विशेष प्रकारका वाक्यहरूको प्रयोगमा

(घ) भाषामिश्रणमा

(ङ) बोल्ने तरिकामा

(च) अन्यमा

८०. तपाईंका भाषिक समुदायका युवायुवतीले आफ्नो भाषा नबोलेर अर्कै भाषा बोलेको सुन्दा कस्तो लाग्छ?

(क) राम्रो (ख) ठिकै (ग) नराम्रो

८१. टिप्पणी (यस अन्तर्वार्तामा कुनै अस्वाभाविक वा उल्लेखनीय कुराहरू भएमा)	
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A. सहयोगका लागि धेरै धेरै धन्यवाद।

Annex C: Sociolinguistic Questionnaire B: Participatory Method

A. Meta data (Baseline information)

Question	Answer
Interview Number	
Date	Day..... Month.....Year..... VS Day.....Month Year..... AD
Place of Interview	Ward: Village/Town: VDC/Municipality: District: Zone: GPS Coordinates:EN
Interviewer Name	(a) (b) (c)

	(d)
	(e)
Language of Elicitation	
Language of Response	
Interpreter Name (if needed)	

It is best if there are 8 to 12 participants for this questionnaire. It can be done with less than 8 people in the group, but is far more reliable with more than 8 people. There should be several women and men in each group. It is also best to have people of all ages (15 years and older) in the group, with several older, middle-aged, and younger subjects.

8. Name of language consultant:
9. (Ask if needed) Sex: (a) Male (b) Female (c) Other
10. Age:
11. Caste/ethnic group:
12. Your mother tongue's name:
13. Your mother's mother tongue.....
14. Your father's mother tongue.....

SCREENING CRITERIA #1: From target MT and at least one parent from target MT.
YES NO

LC#	15.Name	16. Sex	17.Age	18.Caste	19. MT	20. Mother's MT	20. Father's MT	Screening Criteria: Y or N?
1.								
2.								
3.								
4.								
5.								
6.								
7.								
8.								
9.								
10.								
11.								
12.								

15. Where do you live?
(a) Ward No..... (b) Village/Town..... (c) VDC/municipality.....
16. Have you lived anywhere else for more than a year?

- (a) Yes (b) No
 17. (If “Yes”) Where? When? How long did you live there?

SCREENING CRITERIA #2: YES
 NO
 Grew up here, Live here now, and, If they have lived elsewhere, it is not more than 5 years and they have lived in this village for the past 5 years.

LC#	15a. Ward	15b. Village	15c. VDC	16. Elsewhere more than year?	17. Where? When? How long?	Screening Criteria: Y or N?
1.						
2.						
3.						
4.						
5.						
6.						
7.						
8.						
9.						
10.						
11.						
12.						

B. Domains of language use

- A. I speak different languages in different situations, on different occasions and to different people.
- B. On which occasions or to which people, do you usually speak [LWC]? (Place [LWC] label to one side. Participants name domains, write them on paper and place them under [LWC] label)
- C. On which occasions or to which people, do you usually speak [L1]? (Place [L1] label to other side. Participants write domains and place them under [L1]. At this time participants may say “some children speak L1 but others speak LWC.” Ask questions to help them explain which children speak each language, or the situation in which they speak each. Change the labels to show the categories clearly.)
- D. On which occasions or to which people, do you usually speak both [L1] and [LWC]? (Participants write domains, and place them in the middle. They can place them nearer to one side or the other if most people speak a certain language in that domain or if they speak more of that language in that domain but some of the other language.)
- E. Within each of these three main categories, let’s move to the top, the occasions that occur daily and to the bottom the ones that occur rarely. (Put a label for ‘Daily’ and ‘Rarely’ at the top and bottom. Allow them to arrange the domains. Encourage them to leave a gap between the Daily and Rarely categories or place a string.)
- F. (If there many in the daily category) Which are the people you speak to most during a day? Move those slightly higher than any others. (Or place the daily ones in order)

- G. How do you feel about the languages that you use and who you use them with? Would you like to begin using either language more in any other situations?

C. Dialect mapping

- A. What is the name of your language? What is the name of your people? (write all names on a single piece of paper) (If more than one, then for each category ask) Which name is the one you prefer to use?
- i. (Language name preferred by group)...
 - ii. Different names of the language if any (Write these on other pieces of paper & place to the side of their paper).
 - iii. What do speakers of other languages call your language? (Write these on other pieces of paper & place to the side of their paper).
- B. Please name all the Districts/Villages where [L1] is spoken (Write each on a separate piece of paper.) (In some situations, rather than district or village one could ask for the confirmation in this way.
Be sure to get all the following information for each location:
(i) Ward No..... (ii) Village/Town..... (iii) VDC/municipality.....
(iv) District..... (v) Zone.....)
- C. Place these papers on the ground to show which dialects/municipalities/districts are next to each other.
- D. What other languages are so similar to yours that when they speak, you can understand at least some words? (Write these on pieces of paper and add them to the “map” on the ground)
- E. Do any groups of villages all speak [L1] in the same way? (Place a loop of string around each such group)
- F. Which variety do you understand best? Second best? Etc. (Place numbers written on cardboard next to each municipality, language or group of municipalities)
- G. Now we want to show which of these varieties you understand very well, which you don’t understand at all, which you understand most of, but a few words you don’t understand and which you understand only a few words of. In which of these villages can you understand the language Very Well? (Place a Key, have them select the color of plastic marker for “very well”. Have them place those markers on each place they understand “very well.” Repeat for each other category of comprehension.)
- H. Some people have said they want to start writing books* in [L1]. If books were written in [L1], which villages would be able to use those books? (have them put a big string around those varieties) (*If they do not think books can or should be written in their language, then say they want to start making CDs using [L1])
- I. Out of all these you have grouped together, which variety should be used as the one for writing (or recording) [L1] so that all the others will understand it well? If that one could not be used, then which one? (use A, B, and C written on cardboard)

D. Multilingualism

- A. What are the two languages the [L1] people speak the most? This loop will represent the [L1] people who speak [L1] well. This loop will represent the [L1] people who speak [LWC] well. (Lay the circles on the ground)

- B. When I overlap the two circles like this, what does this area where they overlap represent? ([L1] people who speak both [L1] and [LWC] well)
- C. Let's think first about [L1] people who speak [LWC] well. Which types of [L1] people speak [LWC] well? (Have them write on paper).
- D. Before we can put them inside the circle, we need to think whether these people also speak [L1] well, or whether they do not speak [L1] well? Where does each piece of paper belong in the circles? (Have them place the pieces they have written so far. If they want to, they may make the labels more specific or add more labels)
- E. Which [L1] people speak [L1] well, but do not speak [LWC] well? (Have them write the category names and place them in the correct location)
- F. When we think about people in these three different categories, which category has the most [L1] people? How do you feel about that? (let them express their feelings)
- G. Is one of these three groups increasing more than the others? Why is that? How do you feel about that? (Let them express their feelings)

E. Appreciative enquiry

- A. Describe something you saw, heard or did that made you proud of [L1] or your culture or that made you happy to see [L1] used in that way. (write summary labels for each)
- B. How can we take these good things and make them even better? Improve them? Build on them? What are your dreams for your language? (Share in 3s, give time – allow any dream – even impossible ones!)
- C. Let's come back to the big group and listen to the dreams of each small group. Who will write the dreams for the group? Write one dream per paper. (Everyone can help to summarize the dream in 3-4 words. Place each dream under the heading Dreams.)
- D. As we think about your dreams, some seem easy and others seem difficult. Let's put this in order from the 'Easiest' to the most 'Difficult'. (Put down these two labels then let the participants sort the dreams along a continuum.)
- E. Some of these dreams may be more important than others. Still keeping them in order, slide to this side, the ones that are most important. (Let them slide over the ones that they feel are most important. Take a photo now if possible!)
- F. Now you have the chance to begin making plans to make these dreams come true. Which of the dreams do you want to begin making plans for right now? Take the written dream and form a group. (Allow them to form groups. Encourage everyone to join a group)
- G. As you make your plans, think about 1) the steps you need to take, 2) the other people besides who could also be involved and 3) the things you need to begin making this dream happen. (Give them paper and markers to write their plans. Let them write in big letters for the group to see.)
- H. We would like each group to share their plans with all the others. Who would like to share first?

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire B (in Nepali)

छायाकृत कुराहरू मनमनै पढ्ने।

सर्वप्रथम आफ्नो परिचय दिने: मेरो/हाम्रो नाम हो (अरूले पनि आ-आफ्नो परिचय दिने)। हामी त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयको भाषाविज्ञान केन्द्रीय विभागबाट यहाँहरूको भाषाको अध्ययन अनुसन्धानका लागि आएका हौं। यहाँहरूले दिनु भएको भाषा सम्बन्धी जानकारीलाई अरूसँग राख्ने छौं। यसमा यहाँहरूले आफ्नो सहमतिका साथ सहयोग गर्नु हुन्छ भने आशा राखेका छौं।

सहमति: छ छैन

(अ) आधारभूत सूचना

अन्तर्वार्ता भन्दा पहिले तलका प्रश्नहरू (१-७) को उत्तर लेख्नुहोस्।

प्रश्न	उत्तर
१. अन्तर्वार्ता संख्या	
२. मिति	गते.....महिना.....वर्ष..... वि.सं. तारिख.....महिना.....वर्ष.....सन्
३. अन्तर्वार्ता स्थान	क. वार्ड नं.: ख. गाउँ/नगर: ग. गाविस/नगरपालिका: घ. जिल्ला: ङ. अञ्चल: च. जिपिएस कोओर्डिनेट्स:.....पू.उ.

४. अनुसन्धाता(हरू)को नाम:	(क) (ख) (ग) (घ) (ङ)
५. अन्तर्वार्ताको माध्यम भाषा	
६. अन्तरक्रियाको माध्यम भाषा	
७. दोभाषेको नाम (आवश्यक भएमा)	

यस प्रश्नावलीको लागि ८ देखि १२ जनासम्म सहयोगीहरू भए राम्रो हुन्छ। यो ८ जनाभन्दा कम सहभागीहरूसँग पनि गर्न सकिन्छ। तर यदि ८ जनाभन्दा बढीसँग गरियो भने अझै बढी विश्वसनीय हुन्छ। प्रत्येक समूहमा महिला र पुरुष दुवैको लगभग समान सहभागिता हुनु पर्छ। प्रत्येक समूहमा सबै उमेर समूहका (१५ वर्ष देखि माथिका) जसमा केही पाका, केही अधवैसे र केही युवायुवती सहभागीहरू भए राम्रो हुन्छ।

सहयोगी #१:

८. सहयोगी (भाषासूचक) को नाम:

९. (आवश्यक परेमा मात्र) लिङ्ग: (क) पुरुष (ख) महिला (ग) अन्य

१०. उमेर:

११. जाति/जनजाति समूह:

१२. तपाईंको मातृभाषाको नाम:

१३. तपाईंकी आमाको मातृभाषा:

१४. तपाईंको बुबाको मातृभाषा:

छनौटको आधार #१ कम्तीमा बाबु अथवा आमा मध्ये एक मातृभाषी हुनुपर्ने।

छ छैन

भाषा-सूचक	नाम	लिङ्ग	उमेर	जाति	मातृ-भाषा	आमाको मातृभाषा	बुबाको मातृभाषा	छनौटको आधार:

								हो वा होइन?
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११.								
१२.								

१५. तपाईं जन्मेको स्थान/गाउँ कहाँ हो?

(क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:

(ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:

(ङ) अञ्चल:

१६. के तपाईं अन्त कतै गई एक वर्ष भन्दा बढी बस्नु भएको छ?

(क) छ (ख) छैन

१७. (बस्नु भएको छ भने)

(क) कहाँ: (ख) कहिले: (ग) कति समयसम्म:

छनौटको आधार #२ यहीं हुर्केको, अहिले यहीं बसेको, र यदि पाँच वर्ष भन्दा बढी अन्यत्र बसेको भए यहाँ पनि गत पाँच वर्ष देखि नै बसेको हुनु पर्ने।

हो होइन

भाषासूचक	वार्ड नं.	गाउँ	गा.वि.स.	एक वर्ष भन्दा बढी अन्यत्र कतै बस्नु भएको छ?	कहाँ, कहिले र कति समयसम्म	छनौटको आधार: हो वा होइन?
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१२.						

आ) भाषाको प्रयोग

क. म भिन्न परिस्थिति, अवसर र मानिससँग विभिन्न भाषा बोल्छु।

ख. तपाईंहरूले कस्ता मानिस वा अवसरमा प्राय जसो सम्पर्क भाषाको प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ? सम्पर्क भाषाको चिन्ह एक छेउमा राख्नु होस्। सहभागीहरूले भाषा प्रयोगको क्षेत्रहरूका नाम भन्नु हुने छ, कागजमा लेख्नु हुने छ र सम्पर्क भाषाको मुनि राख्नु हुने छ।

ग. तपाईंहरूले कस्तो अवस्थामा वा कस्ता मानिसहरूसँग धेरै जसो मातृभाषा बोल्नु हुन्छ? (मातृभाषाको चिन्ह अर्को छेउमा राख्नु होस्। सहभागीहरूले प्रयोगको क्षेत्रको नाम लेख्नु हुने छ र तिनलाई मातृभाषाको मुनि राख्नु हुने छ। यस पटक सहभागीहरूले "केही बालबालिका मातृभाषा बोल्छन् र केही बालबालिका सम्पर्क भाषा बोल्छन्" भन्नु हुने छ। उहाँहरूको सहयोगको लागि कस्ता बालबालिकाले ती भाषाहरू बोल्छन् वा कस्तो अवस्थामा ती भाषाहरू प्रयोग गर्छन्? समूहहरू राम्ररी देखाउनका लागि चिन्हहरू बदल्नु होस्)

घ. कस्ता मानिससँग र कस्तो अवस्थामा तपाईंहरूले मातृभाषा र सम्पर्क भाषा दुबै बोल्नु हुन्छ? (सहभागीहरूले प्रयोगको क्षेत्रहरू कागजमा लेख्नु हुने छ र तिनलाई बीचमा राख्नु हुने छ। यदि सबै जसो मानिसले त्यो प्रयोग क्षेत्रमा एउटा निश्चित भाषा बोल्छन् वा तिनीहरूले त्यो भाषा बढी बोल्छन् र केही अरू भाषा बोल्छन् भने सहभागीहरूले तिनलाई एक छेउमा वा अर्को छेउमा अझ नजिकै राख्नु हुने छ।)

ड. प्रत्येक समूहमा दैनिक रूपमा प्रयोग हुने अवस्थालाई माथि र कहिलेकाहीं प्रयोग हुनेलाई मुनि राख्नु होस्। (दैनिक र कहिलेकाहींको लागि क्रमशः माथि र तल एउटा एउटा चिन्ह राख्नु होस्। सहभागीहरूलाई प्रयोगका क्षेत्रहरू मिलाउन भन्नु होस्। दैनिक र कहिलेकाहीं समूह बीच ठाउँ छुट्टयाउन उहाँहरूलाई उत्साहित गर्ने वा डोरीले छुट्टयाउन लगाउने काम गर्नु होस्।)

च. (यदि दैनिक प्रयोगमा धेरै प्रयोग क्षेत्र भएमा) सबभन्दा बढी तपाईं कस्तो मानिससँग दैनिक कुराकानी गर्नु हुन्छ? तिनीहरूलाई अरु भन्दा माथि राख्नु होस्। (अथवा दैनिक रूपमा प्रयोग हुनेलाई क्रममा राख्नु होस्।)

छ. तपाईंहरूले प्रयोग गर्ने भाषाहरू र जोसँग ती भाषा प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ उनीहरू प्रति तपाईंको कस्तो सोचाइ छ? के तपाईंले कुनै अर्को अवस्थामा यी मध्ये कुनै भाषा बढी प्रयोग गर्न थाल्नु हुन्छ?

(इ) भाषिकागत सीमा निर्धारण

क. तपाईंहरूको भाषाको नाम के हो? तपाईंहरूको जातिको नाम के हो? (सबै नामहरू कागजको टुक्रामा लेख्नु होस्) (यदि एक भन्दा बढी नाम छन् भने प्रत्येकका लागि सोध्नु होस्) उल्लेखित नाममध्ये तपाईंहरूले कुन नाम बढी रुचाउनु हुन्छ?

१८. (समूहले भन्ने भाषाको नाम).....

१९. तपाईंको भाषा नबोल्ने अन्य भाषा समुदायका मान्छेले तपाईंको भाषालाई के भन्छन्?.....

२०. यो भाषालाई अरु नामले पनि चिनिन्छ?

(क) (ख)

(ग) (घ)

ख. तपाईंहरूको मातृभाषा बोल्ने जिल्ला/गाउँहरूको नाम भन्नु होस् (प्रत्येकको नाम छुट्टै कागजमा लेख्नु होस्।) कतिपय अवस्थामा जिल्ला वा गाउँको सट्टा तपाईंले यसरी सोध्नु सक्नु हुन्छ:

२१. विश्वस्त हुनको लागि प्रत्येक ठाउँका निम्न सूचनाहरू उल्लेख गर्नु होस्:

(क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:

(ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:

(ड) अञ्चल:

ग. ती कागजका टुक्राहरूलाई एक आपसमा नजिक भाषिका/नगरपालिका/जिल्ला अनुसार मिलाएर राख्नु हुने छ।

- घ. तपाईंको भाषासँग मिलने अरू कुन कुन भाषाहरू छन्, जुन त्यो भाषाको वक्ताहरूले बोल्दा तपाईंले कम्तीमा केही शब्दहरू बुझ्नु हुन्छ। (ती भाषाहरूलाई छुट्टै कागजमा लेख्नु होस् र तिनीहरूलाई नक्सामा थप्नु होस्।)
- ङ. गाउँका सबैले आफ्नो भाषा उही प्रकारले बोल्छन्? (त्यस्ता समूहको वरिपरि डोरीले घेरा लगाउनु होस्।)
- च. स्थानीय भेदहरूमध्ये तपाईंले सबैभन्दा राम्रो कुन भेद (भाषा) बुझ्नु हुन्छ? दोस्रो राम्रोसँग बुझ्ने भाषा कुन हो? (कार्डबोर्डमा लेखिएका अंकहरू हरेक क्षेत्र, भाषा, अथवा त्यस क्षेत्रको भाषा समूहको छेउमा राख्नु होस्।)
- छ. अब हामी तपाईंहरूलाई यी भाषिक भेदहरू मध्ये कुन चाहीं राम्ररी बुझ्नु हुन्छ र कुन चाहीं कत्ति पनि बुझ्नु हुन्न? कुन चाहीं सबैभन्दा राम्री बुझ्नु हुन्छ? भन्ने कुरा देखाउन चाहन्छौं। यस्तै गरी कुन भेदका शब्दहरू केही मात्र बुझ्नु हुन्छ त्यो पनि देखाउन चाहन्छौं। यी मध्ये कुन चाहीं गाउँको भाषा धेरै राम्रोसँग बुझ्नु हुन्छ? (चिन्हले देखाउनु होस् र कुनै एउटा रङ्गको चिन्ह छान्न लगाउनु होस्। उनीहरूलाई सबैभन्दा राम्रो बुझ्ने भाषा बोलिने ठाउँमा एउटा चिन्ह राख्न लगाउनु होस्। यसै गरी अन्य भेदहरू माथि पनि चिन्ह राख्न लगाउनु होस्।)
- ज. यी मध्ये तपाईंहरू कुन भेद(भाषा)का वक्ताहरूसँग आफ्नो मातृभाषामा कुरा गर्नु हुन्छ? (यस प्रयोजनका लागि भिन्दै आकार/रङ्गको चिन्हको प्रयोग गर्नु होस्। अर्को चिन्ह राख्नु होस्। (“हामीहरू एक आपसमा कुराकानी गर्दा आफ्नै (एउटै भेद) भाषा बोल्छौं”, “हामी आफ्नै भाषा बोल्छौं, उनीहरू आफ्नै भाषा बोल्छन्”, तिनीहरू अर्को भाषा बोल्छन्, हामीहरू आफ्नै भाषा बोल्छौं” र हामी दुवैले अर्कै भाषा बोल्छौं”)
- झ. केही मानिसहरू आफ्नो भाषामा पाठ्यपुस्तक लेख्न चाहन्छन्। यदि मातृभाषामा किताब लेखियो भने कुन कुन गाउँका विद्यार्थीहरूले प्रयोग गर्न सक्छन् होला? (लेखिएको किताब पढ्न सक्ने गाउँहरूलाई एउटा छुट्टै डोरी भित्र राख्नु होस्।) (यदि किताब लेख्ने र छाप्ने बारेमा सोच्दैनन् भने उनीहरू कुन चाहीं भेदमा सीडी बनाउन चाहन्छन्? भनि सोध्नु होस्।)
- ञ. यी भेदहरू मध्ये लेखन र रेकर्डिङ्ग का लागि कुन चाहींलाई प्रयोग गर्दा सबैले राम्रोसँग बुझ्ने? त्यसो नभएमा कुन चाहीं भाषा प्रयोग हुन सक्छ? (कार्डबोर्डमा लेखिएका ए, बी, सी अक्षरहरूलाई क्रमसँग राख्नु होस्।)

(ई) बहुभाषिकता

- क. तपाईंहरूले सबैभन्दा बढी प्रयोग गर्ने दुईवटा भाषाहरू के के हुन्? एउटा डोरीले मातृभाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्ने व्यक्तिहरूलाई प्रतिनिधित्व गर्छ अर्कोले सम्पर्क भाषा राम्रो बोल्ने व्यक्तिहरूलाई प्रतिनिधित्व गर्छ। (दुईवटै डोरीहरूलाई भूईंमा घेरा बनाएर राख्नु होस्।)

- ख. जब हामीहरूले एउटा डोरीलाई अर्को डोरीमाथि खप्ट्याउँछौं, यो खप्टिएको क्षेत्रले के कुराको प्रतिनिधित्व गर्छ? (यसले मातृभाषा र सम्पर्क भाषा दुईवटै राम्ररी बोल्ने मानिसहरूको प्रतिनिधित्व गर्छ)
- ग. सब भन्दा पहिले हामीहरू सम्पर्क भाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्ने मानिसहरूका बारेमा कुरा गरौं। कस्ता मानिसले सम्पर्क भाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्छन्? (सहभागीहरूलाई कागजका टुक्राहरूमा लेखन लगाउनु होस्)।
- घ. कागजका टुक्राहरूलाई घेराभित्र राख्न लगाउनु भन्दा पहिले उनीहरूले मातृभाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्न जान्दछन् वा जान्दैनन् भन्ने सोच्नु पर्ने हुन्छ। घेरा भित्र प्रत्येक कागजका टुक्राहरू कहाँ पर्छन्? (उनीहरूलाई अहिलेसम्म लेखेका कागजका टुक्राहरू राख्न लगाउनु होस्। उनीहरूले चाहेमा अझ बढी विशिष्ट वा अन्य समूहहरू बनाउन सक्छन्)
- ङ. कस्ता मानिसहरूले मातृभाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्छन् तर सम्पर्क भाषा राम्रोसँग बोल्दैनन्? (उनीहरूलाई त्यस्ता मानिसका समूह लेखन र उपयुक्त ठाउँमा राख्न लगाउनु होस्।)
- च. तीन समूह मध्ये कुनमा सबभन्दा बढी मातृभाषी वक्ताहरू छन्? तपाईंहरू यसलाई कसरी हेर्नु हुन्छ? (सबैभन्दा बढी मातृभाषाका वक्ता भएको घेरो) (उनीहरूलाई आफ्नो विचार व्यक्त गर्न लगाउनु होस्)
- छ. तीनवटै समूह मध्ये कुनै एउटा अन्य दुई समूह बढिरहेको छ कि? किन होला? यसलाई तपाईंहरू कसरी हेर्नु हुन्छ? (उनीहरूलाई आफ्नो विचार व्यक्त गर्न लगाउनु होस्)।

(उ) प्रशंसामूलक सोधखोज

- क. तपाईंहरूले आफ्नो भाषा वा संस्कृतिमा देखेका, सुनेका र गरेका कामले तपाईंलाई गर्वको अनुभव गराउँछ, तिनको उल्लेख गर्नु होस्। मातृभाषाको प्रयोग भइरहेको अवस्था प्रति तपाईं सन्तुष्ट हुनुहुन्छ? (प्रत्येक कामको सारांश लेखन लगाउनु होस्)।
- ख. भइराखेका राम्रा कामहरूलाई कसरी हेर्नुहुन्छ? यसलाई अझ राम्रो कसरी गराउन सकिन्छ? अझ बढी कसरी सुधार्न सकिन्छ? तपाईंहरूको आफ्नो मातृभाषा प्रति के कस्ता आशा-आकाङ्क्षा छन्? (निश्चित समयवधि तोकेर तीनजनाको समूहमा छलफल गर्न लगाउनु होस् - सबै किसिमका आकाङ्क्षामा छलफल गर्न दिनु होस्(असम्भव पनि))।
- ग. प्रत्येक समूहलाई आ-आफ्नो समूहमा छलफल भएका आकाङ्क्षा भन्न लगाउनु होस्। ती आकाङ्क्षा छुट्टाछुट्टै कागजका टुक्राहरूमा एक जनालाई लेखन लगाउनु होस् (ती कागजका टुक्राहरूलाई आकाङ्क्षा लेखिएको शीर्षक मुनि राख्नु होस्)। (सहभागीहरूले व्यक्त गरेका आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई तीन-चार शब्दमा संक्षेपीकरण गर्न लगाउनु होस्)।
- घ. उल्लेख गरिएका आशा-आकाङ्क्षा मध्ये केहीलाई कार्यन्वित गर्न सजिलो र केहीलाई गाह्रो जस्तो देखिन्छ? दुईवटा कागजको टुक्रामा सजिलो र गाह्रो लेखन लगाउनु होस् र तिनीहरूलाई

दुई तिर राखन लगाउनु होस्। आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई सबैभन्दा सजिलो देखि सबैभन्दा गाह्रो क्रममा मिलाएर राखन लगाउनु होस्।

- ड. केही आशा-आकाङ्क्षा अरू भन्दा महत्वपूर्ण जस्तो लाग्छ? सबैभन्दा महत्वपूर्ण आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई एक छेउमा राखन लगाउनु होस्। (छनौट गरिएका महत्वपूर्ण आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई पनि बढी महत्वपूर्ण देखि कम महत्वपूर्णको क्रममा राखन लगाउनु होस्, सम्भव भए एउटा फोटो पनि खिच्नु होस्)।
- च. छनौट गरिएका आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई साकार पार्न योजना बनाउनु होस्। तत्कालै तपाईंहरू कुन आशा-आकाङ्क्षाको योजना बनाउन चाहनु हुन्छ? एक एक समूह बनाउन लगाउनु होस्। प्रत्येक सदस्यलाई समूहमा सक्रिय भएर काम गर्न उत्साहित गर्नु होस् र प्रत्येक आशा-आकाङ्क्षाको योजना तयार गर्नु होस्।
- छ. तपाईंले योजना बनाउँदा यी कुरामा विचार गर्नु होस्: १) तपाईंले चाल्नु पर्ने कदमहरू के के हुन्? २) तपाईं बाहेक संलग्न हुने अरू व्यक्ति को को हुन्? ३) आशा-आकाङ्क्षालाई मूर्त रूप दिन तपाईंहरूलाई चाहिने कुराहरू के के हुन्? (सहभागीहरूलाई कागजका टुक्रा र लेखने सामग्री दिएर ठुला ठुला अक्षरमा योजना लेखन लगाउनु होस्।)
- ज. प्रत्येक समूहलाई आ-आफ्नो समूहमा छलफल भएका योजना भन्न लगाउनु होस्।

सहयोगका लागि धेरै धेरै धन्यवाद।

Annex D: Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C

(For Language Activist or Village Head)

Notes:

Shaded items are NOT to be read aloud.

Introduce yourself first: My/our name is I/we am from Central Department of Linguistics, Tribhuvan University. I am a research assistant of the Linguistic Survey of Nepal. I am here to learn about your language and its situation. We will share the information given by you with others. Are you willing to help us?

INFORMED CONSENT: Given: Not Given:

A. Meta data (Baseline Information)

Enter the answers to the following BEFORE the INTERVIEW:

Question	Answer
Interview Number	
Date	Day..... Month.....Year..... VS Day.....Month Year..... AD
Place of Interview	Ward No: Village/Town: VDC/Municipality: District: Zone: GPS Coordinates:EN
Interviewer Name	(a) (b)

5. Name of language consultant:

6. (Ask if needed) Sex: (a) Male (b) Female (c) Other

7. Age:

8. Caste:
9. Ethnic group:
10. Your mother tongue's name:
11. Name given by the nonnative speakers for your language
12. Different names of the language if any?
 (i)..... (ii)
 (iii)..... (iv)
13. Your mother's mother tongue.....
14. Your father's mother tongue.....
15. What village were you born in?
 (a) Ward No..... (b)Village/Town..... (c)VDC/municipality.....
16. Where do you live now?
17. How many years have you lived here?
18. Other ethnic groups residing in your area: (enter below)
19. Other languages spoken by those groups: (enter below)

	18. Ethnic Group:	19. Language:
a.		
b.		
c.		
d.		
e.		
f.		

20. Should anything be done to preserve or promote your mother tongue?
 (a) Yes (b) No
21. (If "Yes"): In what ways do you think you can support the preservation and promotion of your mother tongue?
- (a) by devising the script?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (b) by making the spelling system systematic?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (c) by compiling dictionary?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (d) by writing grammar?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (e) by encouraging people to write literature in mother tongue?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (f) by writing and publishing textbooks?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (g) by publishing newspapers?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (h) by making use of the language in administration?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (i) by making use of the language in the medium of instruction at primary level?
 (a) Yes (b) No
- (j) in any other ways?

Proceed to ask individual Sociolinguistic Questionnaire A, if appropriate.

Sociolinguistic Questionnaire C (in Nepali)

(भाषिक अभियन्ता (आन्दोलनका अगुवा) र गाउँका मुखियाका लागि)

छायांकृत कुराहरू मनमनै पढने।

सर्वप्रथम आफ्नो परिचय दिने: मेरो/हाम्रो नाम हो। (अरूले पनि आ-आफ्नो परिचय दिने)। हामी त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय भाषाविज्ञान केन्द्रीय विभागबाट यहाँहरूको भाषाको अध्ययन अनुसन्धानका लागि आएका हौं। यहाँहरूले दिनुभएको भाषासम्बन्धी जानकारीलाई अरूसँग राख्ने छौं। यसमा यहाँहरूले आफ्नो सहमतिका साथ सहयोग गर्नु हुन्छ भने आशा राखेका छौं।

सहमति: छ छैन

(अ) आधारभूत सूचना

अन्तर्वार्ता भन्दा पहिले तलका प्रश्नहरू (१-७) को उत्तर लेख्नु होस्।

प्रश्न	उत्तर
१. अन्तर्वार्ता संख्या	
२. मिति	गते..... महिना.....वर्ष..... वि.सं. तारिख.....महिना वर्ष..... सन्
३. अन्तर्वार्ता स्थान	क. वार्ड नं.: ख. गाउँ/नगर: ग. गाविस/नगरपालिका: घ. जिल्ला: ड. अञ्चल: च. जिपिएस कोओर्डिनेट्स:.....पू.उ.
४. अनुसन्धाता(हरू)को नाम:	(क) (ख)

५. भाषासूचकको नाम:
६. (आवश्यक भएमा मात्र) लिङ्ग: (क) पुरुष (ख) महिला (ग) अन्य
७. उमेर:
८. जात:
९. जातजातिको समुह:
१०. तपाईंको मातृभाषाको नाम:
११. तपाईंको भन्दा अन्य भाषा समुदायका (तपाईंको भाषा नबोल्ने) मान्छेले तपाईंको भाषालाई के भन्छन्?.....
१२. यो भाषालाई अरु नामले पनि चिनिन्छ? (यो भाषाको अरु के के नाम छन्?)
 (क) (ख)
 (ग) (घ)
१३. तपाईंकी आमाको मातृभाषा:
१४. तपाईंका बुबाको मातृभाषा:
१५. तपाईं जन्मेको स्थान/गाँउ कहाँ हो?
 (क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:
 (ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:
 (ङ) अञ्चल:
१६. हाल तपाईं कहाँ बस्नु हुन्छ?
- (क) वार्ड नं.: (ख) गाउँ/नगर:
 (ग) गाविस/नगरपालिका: (घ) जिल्ला:
 (ङ) अञ्चल:
१७. तपाईं यहाँ बस्नु भएको कति समय भयो?
१८. तपाईंको गाउँ/छरछिमेकमा बसोबास गर्ने अन्य जातजाति: (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)
१९. तिनीहरूले बोल्ने अन्य भाषा: (तलको तालिकामा लेख्नु होस्)

क्र.सं.	१८. जातजाति	१९. भाषा
क.		
ख.		
ग.		
घ.		
ङ.		
च.		

२०. तपाईंको मातृभाषा संरक्षण तथा सम्बर्द्धनका लागि केही गर्नु पर्छ?
 (क) पर्छ (ख) पर्दैन

२१. (पछ्छ भन्ने): तपाईंले आफ्नो मातृभाषाको संरक्षण र सम्बर्धनको लागि केकस्ता काम गरेर सहयोग गर्न सक्नु हुन्छ?

- (क) लिपि विकासको लागि काम गरेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (ख) हिज्जेलाई व्यवस्थित गरेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (ग) शब्दकोष बनाएर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (घ) व्याकरण लेखेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (ङ) मातृभाषामा साहित्य लेख्न उत्साहित गरेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (च) पाठ्यपुस्तक लेखन तथा प्रकाशन गरेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (छ) पत्रपत्रिका निकालेर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (ज) प्रशासनमा प्रयोग गर्न लगाएर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (झ) प्राथमिक तहमा माध्यमको रूपमा प्रयोग गर्न लगाएर
(अ) सक्छु (आ) सकिदैन
- (ञ) अन्य प्रकारले:

उपयुक्त भएमा समाज-भाषावैज्ञानिक प्रश्नावली भर्न शुरु गर्ने।